

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

Technical Report for period
1/1/2022 – 31/12/2022

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1 INTRODUCTION

CO2-SPICER project was officially launched on 1 November 2020 and its implementation has been planned for 3.5 years. It is being carried out by a consortium of 5 organisations from the Czech Republic and Norway under the leadership of Czech Geological Survey. For the purposes of this report, Project Partners’ acronyms were used (Tab. 1-1).

Tab. 1-1: Acronyms of Project Partners used in the report.

Project Partner	Acronym
Czech Geological Survey	CGS
MND a.s.	MND
NORCE Norwegian Research Centre AS	NORCE
VSB – Technical University of Ostrava	VSB
Institute of Geophysics of the Czech Academy of Sciences	GFU

The project is divided into 10 Work Packages (Fig. 1-1). Each Work Package has its clearly defined leader, objectives, description of work and results. Work packages are structured into Tasks, each with a defined Task leader.

Fig. 1-1: Project structure of CO2-SPICER.

The work in the 2nd project period was fully oriented to the achievement of the main project objective – preparation of a pilot CO₂ storage project at the Zar-3 field in SE Czech Republic. Significant progress in this direction has been made in all Work Packages.

The work was governed by the detailed work plan described in the document “Project content & Detailed description of Work Packages” (attachment 5 to project application). Chapter 2 of this report follows the defined project structure and describes the work progress in each Work Package and Task in detail.

2 DESCRIPTION OF THE PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

2.1 WORK PACKAGE 1 – Data gathering and consolidation

Summary

The main goal of WP1 is to obtain suitable data for the description, assessment and screening of the Zar-3 pilot storage site. These data sources have been used as inputs during the development of a three-dimensional static geological model of the storage site and complex (WP2), dynamic modelling (WP3), risk assessment (WP6) and monitoring (WP7). The required data have been obtained from both publicly available sources (in particular CGS databases) and the archive and databases of the industrial Project Partners (and current Zar-3 field operator) MND. All collected data have been consolidated and unified (Task 1.1). Task 1.2 is reserved for collection and analysis of well cores. The overview of all collected data is kept using a dedicated project geodatabase and GIS (Task 1.3). The work in WP1 was carried out by CGS (WP leader) and MND according to the plan; some issues were caused by the consequences of the tornado of 2021, which destroyed the MND core repository in Lužice.

Task 1.1 – Collection, consolidation and unification of existing data, site characterization

Main part of Task 1.1 has been completed in 2021. Nevertheless, collection, verification and consolidation of remaining input data continued in 2022 according to the needs of the other technical Work Packages (WP2-WP8), for example data of well integrity logging on well UH67H. All maps, prepared in 2021 were updated and uploaded to the project geodatabase (see Task 1.3).

Basic site characterization with the purpose to gather and process the main geographical and geological data on the storage site was completed and the corresponding result R1.2 “Report on pedology, geology, geomorphology, climatology, conflict of interest and nature protection” was submitted in March 2022.

Some of the maps compiled in 2021 that will be part of the project result TO01000112-V3 (Set of thematic maps of the CO₂ Zar-3 storage site; type N_{map}) that is planned to be submitted in 2023 were graphically and formally adjusted and prepared to a final form ready for submission.

The data described above, together with all additional data gathered, measured or otherwise established in the course of the project, are continuously stored in the project geodatabase (a spatial geodatabase in which geographical and spatial information are stored for future reference) that has been created as part of Task 1.3. To ensure that all project data share a unified geographic framework, a basic coordinate system (S42) was defined at the start of the project. All project data have been and will be converted to this system.

Task 1.1 has been carried out by CGS in cooperation with MND.

Task 1.2 – Overview of available cores and their documentation, sampling selection

The goal of this Task is to access suitable core and cuttings materials in MND core repository for further analyses and take core samples needed for various laboratory experiments and tests (WP4, WP5).

Following the first core inspection and sampling campaign in 2021, when 62 core boxes containing cores from wells located in the Zar-3 site and its vicinity were selected for sampling, a second campaign was performed in 2022. It was mainly oriented at caprock samples, since the evaluation of the first set of geomechanical experiments in WP4 revealed insufficient amount of information from caprock.

Within this second campaign, eight additional core boxes were selected for sampling. The selection of suitable rock cores was very difficult because many core boxes were destroyed during the tornado in 2021. Some of the “newly” selected core boxes originated from wells from analogue sites in wider area of Zar-3, providing core material from geological formations analogous to those present at Zar-3 (Tab. 2.1-1).

Tab. 2.1-1: List of new drilling core samples.

Well name	Core No	Box No	Measured depth (m)	Stratigraphy	Caprock/reservoir
MIL1	1	1	942	Mikulov Fm.	Caprock
KOE6	10	2	1501	Carboniferous	Caprock
UH16	6	1	2077	Carboniferous	Caprock
UH17	5	3	2914	Mikulov Fm.	Caprock
UH27	8	2	1857	Carboniferous	Caprock
ZA3	6	4	1886	Carboniferous	Caprock
ZA4	1	5	1866	Paleogene	Caprock
ZA5H	1	2	2095	Mikulov Fm.	Caprock

At the end of 2022, a collection of cuttings (rock fragments separated from drilling mud) from well ZA3 was prepared by MND and provided to CGS for further analyses that will mainly serve as input for assessment of caprock integrity within risk assessment (WP6).

All selected core boxes and taken core samples are registered in a special “master table” to keep the overview and follow the progress of utilization of individual samples and results of laboratory experiments.

Task 1.2 has been carried out by MND in cooperation with CGS.

Task 1.3 – Creation of a project geodatabase (database + GIS)

The project geodatabase, created by CGS in Task 1.3 in 2021, has been kept up-to-date in 2022 by continuous upload of data gathered in Task 1.1 and well core data gathered in Task 1.2, as well as all other data gathered and created during realization of other WPs. All data designated for upload are verified, analysed and stored in the geodatabase for future use. In this way, the geodatabase is serving as the main project data source for all Work Packages. It is available online for all Project Partners, respecting, at the same time, the access rights, limited in some cases by the provisions of the Non-disclosure Agreement between MND and research partners of the project.

For selected spatial GIS data, an ArcGIS Online solution is available for presenting and sharing data with all Project Partners. In 2022, the following map layers were made available via ArcGIS Online:

- Area of interest and Administrative division (see Fig. 2.1-1)
- Agricultural land protection classes
- Biogeography and climate
- Hydrogeology and hydrography
- Geomorphology
- Land-cover and Landscape
- Landslides
- Land-use (status 2020)
- Mineral resources (hydrocarbons)
- Potential threat to agricultural soils (erosion)
- Selected species and transnational nature protection
- Soil map (pedology)
- Territorial and species nature protection (see Fig. 2.1-2)
- Territorial system of ecological stability

Fig. 2.1-1: Administrative map of the area with demarcation of the area of interest and administrative division.

Fig. 2.1-2: Example of map of conflicts of interest with nature protection: territorial and species protection of nature.

No changes were made in the Data Management Plan in 2022.

Work in Task 1.3 has been carried out by CGS.

Deviations and changes

The only deviation from the plan was the interruption of core inspection and sampling activities in Task 1.2 due to the damage of the MND core repository at Lužice caused by the tornado in June 2021. Its consequences, in particular a complete loss of part of the core material and the inaccessibility of the core repository due to reconstruction works influenced the project work in 2022 as well.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

Other results	
Result title	Date of submission
R1.2 Report on pedology, geology, geomorphology, climatology, conflict of interest and nature protection.	03/2022 (English version 12/2022)

Milestones

No milestones are defined for this Work Package.

2.2 WORK PACKAGE 2 – 3D geological model of the storage complex

Summary

The main goal of this Work Package is to develop a static 3D geological model of the storage complex with particular focus on storage reservoir properties, using seismic and other geophysical data, geological interpretations and well data acquired during WP1. In addition, a larger, simplified model that includes the reservoir overburden shall be constructed to analyse the risks of fluid migration into shallow aquifers (to be analysed WP6).

The WP2 work in 2022 was generally performed according to the plan, with some slight delays in reporting. A detailed static 3D geological model of the Zar-3 reservoir and a simplified regional 3D geological model of the area were finalised by MND (WP leader) and CGS, respectively, with contributions by the NORCE to both interpretation versions. An important activity was to finish and optimize the reservoir model in several iterations to fit the WP3 dynamic modelling group needs. Similarly, several iterations of the fracture model (result R2.4) were prepared to find the best solution for implementation of fracture intensities to the 3D static reservoir model.

Fig. 2.2-1: Final 3D static geological model in broader area of the Zar-3 site.

Task 2.1 – Interpretation and modelling of the reservoir zone, overlying and underlying rocks and faults

In 2022, the geological interpretations of 3D seismic data together with the well data and their time to depth conversions were thoroughly discussed by the MND-NORCE modelling team. The final version (see example in Fig. 2.2.-2) was used as input for

construction of the 3D static geological model in Task 2.3. Contour maps of individual stratigraphic formations were prepared to support preparation of the formal WP2 results (mainly V1 and R2.2). Minor interpretational changes were made, based on the needs of the WP3 dynamic modelling group.

Fig. 2.2-2: Final seismic interpretation of Zar-3 storage area displayed on cross-line 2630.

Seismic interpretation for the regional model was finalised by CGS, using the OpendTect software. Selected horizons mapped in the 3D cube included base of the Flysch Belt units, base of the Paleogene, top of the Jurassic Vranovice formation, base of the Jurassic and base of the Carboniferous (Fig. 2.2-3).

Fig. 2.2-3: 3D view of interpreted stratigraphic surfaces in time domain: base of the Flysch Belt units (A), base of the Paleogene (B), base of the Jurassic (C), base of the Carboniferous (D).

Subsequent conversion of time horizons to the depth domain was performed using average velocity maps constructed on the base of values of stratigraphic / lithostratigraphic boundaries in wells, which were refined several times during the course of the work by detailed correlation of well data. After the depth conversion, a number of manual adjustments based on well results were made and detailed depth structure maps of top surfaces and bases of all selected stratigraphic / lithostratigraphic boundaries were produced (Fig. 2.2-4). The final result of the geological interpretation is a series of 13 depth structure maps: base of the Flysch Belt units, top and base of the Paleogene, top and base of the Jurassic, top and base of the Mikulov formation, top and base of the Vranovice formation, top and base of the Nikolčice formation, top and base of the Carboniferous. All structure maps were also produced in a version with a detailed indication of the extent of the overlying and underlying lithostratigraphic units. The maps represent an important part of the result V1 (see details below).

Fig. 2.2.-4: Examples of constructed structure maps: top of the Vranovice formation (A), top of the Vranovice formation with the extent of the overlying units (B), base of the Vranovice formation (C), base of the Vranovice formation with the extent of the underlying units (D).

Thickness maps (Fig. 2.2-5) of individual lithostratigraphic units were also produced by CGS and partly used to check the correctness of the structure maps. The set of created maps includes: thickness map of the Paleogene, thickness map of the Mikulov formation, thickness map of the Vranovice formation, thickness map of the Nikolčice formation and thickness map of the Carboniferous. Additionally, for risk assessment purposes in WP6, a combined caprock thickness map was created, including both Paleogene and the Mikulov formation.

Fig. 2.2-5: Examples of constructed thickness maps: thickness map of the Paleogene (left) and thickness map of the Jurassic Mikulov formation (right).

Main outcomes of Task 2.1 were summarized in result R2.2 “3D geometric model with interpreted surfaces and bases of selected horizons, settled wells and fault planes” that was submitted in May 2022.

Task 2.2 – Lithofacies analysis

Analysis of lithofacial types of rocks building the Zar-3 storage complex was based on well logs and mud logs tied with seismic data, as well as on the core sample analyses.

Fig. 2.2-6: 3D representation of Lower Carboniferous “flysch” or turbidite facies of the Myslejovice Fm. and dolomitic sandstone shallow marine facies of Middle Jurassic Nikolčice Fm.

Fig. 2.2-7: 3D representation of Upper Jurassic patch reef and carbonate bank facies of the Vranovice Fm. overlying the Nikolčice Fm.

The lithofacial model deals with the reservoir horizon and underlying and overlying seal strata. Its main purpose is to improve the input data for the reservoir dynamic modelling and CO₂ storage simulations. Good knowledge of lithofacies patterns makes it possible to interpolate and extrapolate rock types and reservoir or sealing properties to the undrilled parts of the storage site. The facial model of the Zar-3 storage site is shown as 4 layers in Figs. 2.2-6 – 2.2-9.

In the Upper Jurassic, shallow sea covered the Zar-3 area, and the principal reservoir – the dolomites of the Vranovice Fm. - were deposited in patch reef and carbonate bank facies. The original limestones were dolomitized during the early diagenetic phase. Rich microscopic documentation of the rocks has been prepared in an atlas showing the details of the rock types as a supporting material for the facial model of the storage site.

Fig. 2.2-8: In the Upper Jurassic, the Mikulov Fm. was deposited in basinal marl facies of the upper continental slope.

Little or no evidence has been found of an erosional contact of the Vranovice Fm. and the overlying Mikulov Fm. These basinal marls with little or no dolomitization were deposited in the upper continental slope facies. In the Zar-3 storage complex the Mikulov Fm. represents the seal together with the Nesvačilka Fm. (Figs. 2.2-8 and 2.2-9).

Fig. 2.2-9: In the Eocene, the Nesvačilka Fm., Žarošice Mb., was deposited in submarine canyon facies with steep flanks and slumps.

Facial maps were composed for Zar-3 storage site and the adjacent area to provide basis of better understanding of the spatial distribution of the permeable and non-permeable rocks and a prediction, what will happen during and after the CO₂ storage in broader context.

The results of Task 2.2 are summarized in result R2.3 “Lithofacial layer model” that was finalised and submitted with some delay in December 2022.

Task 2.3 – Construction of the static model

The inputs from Tasks 2.1 and 2.2 were used for construction of the static reservoir model. The final model was prepared in several versions. Each model iteration (version) was carefully tested in cooperation with WP3 modelling group to get the best interconnection of the static geological model output and the real well results obtained during the oil and gas production. Finally, a 10x10 m cell density grid with vertical cells resolution of 1 m was prepared for the handover of the model data to the WP3 dynamic modelling team (Fig. 2.2-10). This final resolution will be coarsened in the aquifer part by the dynamic modellers to get an acceptable grid resolution for CO₂ injection simulations.

Fig. 2.2-10: Result of final seismic interpretation – 3D model of the Zar-3 reservoir with 10x10 m grid and 1 m vertical cells resolution.

For construction of the regional geological model, the depth contours of the individual maps (surfaces) from Task 2.1 were gridded within the extent of 3D seismic cube with 10 x 10 m increment and displayed in 3D (Fig. 2.2-11). Three different types of SW (OpendTect, MOVE, Petrel) were tested and used for 3D visualization and further modelling work; the SW export and import functions allowed for smooth transfer of the data among the individual SW environments.

Fig. 2.2-11: 3D view of mapped surfaces in depth domain in OpendTect (left) and in MOVE (right).

A 3D grid with a grid increment of 10 m and a vertical depth range of 0 - 3000 m (TVDSS) was created in Petrel software. All surfaces from previous interpretations and mapping were added to the 3D grid and zones were created between them, representing geological / stratigraphic units (Fig. 2.2-12).

Fig. 2.2-12: Regional geological model in Petrel: 3D views of the reservoir - Vranovice Fm. (left) and the caprock (Mikulov Fm. and Paleogene) sealing the Vranovice Fm. (right).

The outcomes of Task 2.3 represent the main part of the result TO01000 112-V1 “3D geological model of the storage complex and set of structural geological maps” (type Nmap) – one of the main Project Results and the key achievement of WP3. The result was finalised in June 2023 and after some formal improvement submitted as part of the 2022 Interim Report. The result was subject to an internal quality control procedure at MND; the corresponding QC opinion is enclosed as attachment to the main result document.

Task 2.4 – Fracture analysis and modelling

Construction of the detailed fracture model in the Petrel software was finalised in 2022, in cooperation of CGS and MND. The standard fracture modelling algorithm was used firstly, but as the unwieldy numbers of fractures led to impossibility to upscale them into the final grid, the simplified fracture model algorithm was implemented in the end. The lack of input data, especially core data for estimation of suitable fault apertures, led to problems with defining of correct apertures to get realistic porosities and permeabilities in the 3D domain of the Zar-3 reservoir. Finally, an alternative approach was implemented to get realistic petrophysical properties for the 3D static geological model of the reservoir, lying in the use of fracture intensities distribution calibrated to porosities and permeabilities interpreted from the well logs. Along with several iterations of distribution of standard petrophysical properties (derived from well logs; see Task 2.5), also the fracture intensities distributions in the 3D space of the Zar-3 reservoir were handed over to the WP3 dynamic modelling team. This provided the opportunity to precise the final petrophysical properties distribution in the areas where the well tests together with increased well productivities are pointing to high values of permeability. These local occurrences of high permeability zones - in case of Zar-3 as a partly fractured reservoir - cannot be covered only by calculations of petrophysical properties using the well log interpretations and need to adjusted during the history match process. The fracture modelling workflow is illustrated in Fig. 2.2-13.

Fig. 2.2-13: Fracture modelling workflow showing fracture intensities upscaled to the model grid: a) FMS fractures on wells color-coded by the fracture system; b) fracture intensities upscaled into the model grid; c) fractures generated using a stochastic model based on FMS data; d) example of the first fracture system intensities distributed into the whole grid based on its statistical characteristics; e) fracture model where the coverage of the whole grid was achieved by increased size of fractures; f) fracture model based on fracture intensities distributed over the whole grid.

Results of Task 2.4 are summarized in result R2.4 “Model of spatial distribution and properties of fractures” that was submitted in June 2022

Task 2.5 – Distribution of petrophysical properties and fluids

Distribution of petrophysical properties

After the upscale of all available well logs within the model grid the distribution of porosity and permeability in the final model grid from Task 2.3 was done. Since the static model deals mostly with the carbonate type of reservoir in a relatively large area with only locally denser dataset, the Gaussian sequential simulation was chosen as the most suitable property distribution method. It is a stochastic method based on kriging but capable of capturing extreme values in a heterogenous reservoir. The properties should honour the well results, histogram and variogram with same variability image over the model. Firstly, variograms and variogram maps were constructed and anisotropy was tested for the dataset that was upscaled from values calculated from well logs. Several major direction azimuths were tested in the variograms, ranging from 0 to 35 degrees. Anisotropy range was tested with values from 250 m to 2500 m in major direction and

150 m to 2500 m in minor direction, using the spherical variogram. Finally, as the only denser part of the dataset is concentrated in the segment covering just the direct vicinity of the Zar-3 CO₂ storage and the data in the rest of the aquifer are rather scarce, the isotropic distribution with the anisotropy range 1250 m in both directions was used for both reservoir zones. Final iterations used horizontal grid density of 10x10 m with either 1 m layer thickness following the base of the reservoir zone, or 1 m layer thickness with horizontal layering. All different distributions were also gradually tested by reservoir engineers to match the known volume of hydrocarbons and to match the production results in the discrete parts of the grid penetrated by the production wells. In the end, the 10 x10 m grid with follow-base layering was chosen as working option, with the supplementary option using 10 x10 m grid with horizontal layering (Fig. 2.2-14).

Fig. 2.2-14: 3D model with porosity distribution using subhorizontal layering, 10x10 m grid and 1 m thickness of layers.

Results of this part of the work were resumed in result R2.5 “Model and maps of basic petrophysical distribution in the storage complex” that was submitted in April 2022 and updated in December 2022.

Maps of initial and current contacts of fluids in the reservoir

After detailed interpretation of 3D seismic, construction of surfaces of key horizons (Task 2.1), construction of the static reservoir model (Task 2.3) and petrophysical properties distribution (Task 2.5) in Petrel software, the next step in WP3 workflow was the construction of maps of original and recent fluid contacts. The tops of the reservoir formation within the final model grid served as the main input for the map construction. The original depths of the contacts of oil, gas and water were derived from the well log interpretation reports by Hrubý (2004 and 2011¹). The recent contact levels (Fig. 2.2-15) were derived from interpretation of recent neutron logs from the ZA3 well.

¹ Hrubý, J. (2004). Závěrečná zpráva. Petrofyzikální analýza ropo-plynového ložiska Žarošice. MS. MND a.s. archive, Hodonín.

Fig. 2.2-15: Zar-3 oil and gas field. Depth map of Vranovice Fm. top with recent (2022) position of gas, oil and water zones.

Results of this part of the work were summarized in result R2.6 “Maps of initial and current contacts of fluids in the reservoir” that was finalised in April 2022.

Vertical temperature model

The vertical temperature model was built by CGS as a part of the static geometric model of the storage complex and serves as an input for the dynamic modelling in WP3.

Reservoir temperature in the Vranovice Fm. measured by the downhole thermometer in the ZA3 well ranges from 50.2 to 54.0 °C at depths from 1615 to 1800 m (measured from the surface). The calculated geothermal gradient ranges from 21.2 to 24.7 mK.m⁻¹. The values are notably lower than the average global geothermal gradient 33 mK.m⁻¹. The average annual surface (neutral zone) temperature ranges from 8 to 9 °C and represents the starting temperature value. Simplified vertical temperature model of the Zar-3 site is shown in Fig. 2.2-16.

Hrubý, J. (2011). Závěrečná zpráva. Dodatečné vyhodnocení vrtů Za9Ah a Za14H a MDT měření ve vrtu Za6a, ložisko Žarošice. MS. MND a.s. archive, Hodonín.

Fig. 2.2-16: Simplified vertical temperature model of the Zar-3 site with well trajectories, well logs and geological units building the CO₂-storage complex. The red rectangle shows the reservoir temperature and depth interval.

A thermal history model for the ZA3 well was prepared using the PetroMod software. It provides a complete depth profile of thermal conductivity and heat capacity. This may be used for further dynamic modelling of CO₂ injection associated with cooling of the rocks (WP8).

Results of this activity are presented in result R2.7 “Vertical temperature model” that was submitted in June 2022. This report, similarly to all other results finalised in 2022, is enclosed as attachment to the 2022 Interim Report.

Deviations and changes

The work in WP2 was broadly performed in accord with the plan. Milestone M2.1 “Handover of the static geological model for dynamic modelling and simulations in WP3”

was achieved as planned in March 2022. All results planned for 2022 were submitted. Some delays were encountered in Tasks 2.2 and 2.5, and generally in formal finalisation of the reports. Some results were, therefore, submitted with several months of delay. This has not influenced any follow-up activities in other Work Packages, also because the working results were transferred to other WPs immediately after their achievement.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

Main results		
No.	Result title	Date of submission
TO01000 112-V1	3D geological model of the storage complex and set of structural geological maps	06/2022

Other results		
No.	Result title	Date of submission
R2.2	3D geometric model with interpreted surfaces and bases of selected horizons, settled wells and fault planes (Task 2.1)	05/2022
R2.3	Lithofacial layer model (Task 2.2)	12/2022
R2.4	Model of spatial distribution and properties of fractures (Task 2.4)	06/2022
R2.5	Maps of basic petrophysical properties distribution in the storage complex (Task 2.5)	04/2022
R2.6	Maps of initial and current contacts of fluids in the reservoir (Task 2.5)	04/2022
R2.7	Vertical temperature model (Task 2.5)	06/2022

Milestones

Milestone	Date	Description
M2.1	achieved 03/2022	Handover of the static geological model for dynamic modelling and simulations in WP 3

2.3 WORK PACKAGE 3 – Dynamic modelling and simulations

Summary

The main objectives of WP3 are: (i) assembling and history matching of full-field reservoir model of the planned storage site, and (ii) simulation of different options of CO₂ injection pilot accounting for most important effects related to CO₂ storage in fractured carbonate reservoir. The work within WP3 followed up the work initiated in 2021 and was generally performed according to the plan, with some delays. One of the planned milestones (M3.1) was achieved on time while the other one (M3.2) had to be postponed to 2023. Despite the fact that work in several Tasks is slightly behind schedule, the prospects to achieve WP objectives in the remaining part of the project are still good. The work in WP3 was performed by MND (WP leader) and NORCE.

Task 3.1 – Import of upgraded 3D model and upscaling

The geological model constructed in WP2 and transferred to WP3 (achievement of Milestone M3.1) was assembled using a fine grid with the goal to cover detailed reservoir properties distributions in 3D. Size of individual grid blocks was 10 x 10 x 1 m. The geological model includes not only the reservoir geo-body, but also the adjacent aquifer. It contains 15.5 million of grid blocks (see Fig. 2.3-1).

Fig. 2.3-1: Geological model – porosity distribution.

Obviously, the grid with so many grid blocks is not convenient for running dynamic reservoir simulations on commonly used computers. That's why geological model upscaling to a model with less grid blocks is a common practice in the process of static model conversion into the dynamic one. Porosity, permeability, and fracture intensity were upscaled to grid blocks with dimensions 10 x 10 x 5 m, meaning that only vertical upscaling from 1 to 5 meters was done. Fig. 2.3-2 illustrates both grids before (left) and after (right) upscaling.

Fig. 2.3-2: Cross-section through the model before (left) and after (right) upscaling.

The upscaled model still contains 3.2 million grid blocks. Only a part of the grid blocks was left active for further work in dynamic modelling to reduce the model size. The reduced grid contained the hydrocarbon-saturated part of the reservoir (central part) and the nearest part of the aquifer. The rest of the aquifer volume that is in communication with the central part of the reservoir was simulated by introducing the Fetkovich analytical aquifer in the Eclipse simulator. The volume of the water contained in the analytical aquifer and the degree of aquifer support (productivity index = influx rate per unit pressure difference) were tuned during history matching. Number of active grid blocks in the reduced model reached 180,000, which is a reasonable number for running simulations. Fig. 2.3-3 illustrates both the size of the reduced model used as a dynamic model and saturation with reservoir fluids (gas cap in red; oil zone in green; aquifer in blue).

Fig. 2.3-3: Extent of the model used for simulation (with reduced number of grid blocks in the aquifer).

After the model upscaling, PVT fluids properties (based on results of the PVT part of Task 3.3), rock physics functions (relative permeabilities), production history (volumes

and pressures), well completions (intervals opened for production), etc. were integrated into the reservoir simulations.

Task 3.2 – Dynamic data analysis to evaluate well-reservoir and fracture network parameters

This Task is focusing on (i) interpretation of available well test and monitoring data (dynamic data) to evaluate well and reservoir parameters for further reservoir simulations; (ii) designing and carrying out of step rate test of an injection well to understand reservoir response to higher rates (in comparison with current operations) and dynamic behaviour of fracture network (presumably providing majority of permeability of this fractured reservoir), and (iii) coupling of the well test design and dynamic data interpretation with geomechanics assessments in in WP4.

During the 2nd reporting period NORCE have finished analysis of available dynamic data on the field. Interpretation of available well tests and monitoring data (dynamic data) provided estimations of well-reservoir parameters for wells ZA3, ZA5H, ZA4A, ZA9AH and ZA7 (see Fig. 2.3.-4). The interpretation provided description of the reservoir flow capacity for each of the wells. The measured pressure transients in the well and uncertainty with flowing rate data reduced accuracy of the estimated well-reservoir parameters. Thus, a significant uncertainty in the flow capacity estimations is reported based on analysis of the noise in the pressure data. However, the flow capacity estimates look as the most reliable values for conditioning of the reservoir model. These estimates account for fracture permeability overlooked in the lab measurements, providing also the trend of changes of the permeability-thickness product through the reservoir.

Task 4.4 of WP4 provided evaluation of tensile and shear failures for the intact reservoir rocks based on the results of the laboratory experiments. This evaluation indicated that both failure mechanisms would not be activated for the pressures between the initial and current reservoir pressures. This argues, in particular, that the natural fractures present in the reservoir are geomechanically closed at the initial pressure. In such case, fractures may still provide quite large permeability compared to the porous matrix, but pressure/stress sensitivity of the fracture permeability may be limited.

Well monitoring data, available for the initial period of production, did not reveal significant changes in reservoir (including fracture) permeability, although these data characterize very limited pressure range. The Step Rate Test (SRT) planned for the injection well ZA7 in 2021 and postponed to 2023 due to problems with the well completion (see sub-chapter “Deviations and changes” for more details) remains crucial for clarifying dynamic fracture behaviour for pressure build-up above the initial reservoir pressure due to injection. The SRT and its interpretation is the only remaining activity in T3.2 causing continuation of the task in 2023.

Fig. 2.3-4: Well locations and flow capacity (kh) estimated from interpretation of the dynamic data for wells ZA3, ZA5H, ZA4A, ZA9AH and ZA7.

Task 3.3 – Upscaling of geochemical, geomechanical and compositional effects

During the 2nd reporting period NORCE have created a new PVT model based on the fluid study report from PGNIG². The data from the report was digitalized and entered into PVTsim Nova software rev. 5.1.220, which was used to create and tune the PVT model, as well as for output of the results in E300 (compositional) and E100 (blackoil) models. The created model shows a good match with properties measured at different temperatures. It should be mentioned that interaction of reservoir fluids with CO₂ was not studied experimentally, therefore the miscibility was estimated based on literature correlations³.

The blackoil realization was tested against the compositional one with the conclusion that the blackoil model with properly set SOLVENT option should be sufficient for fulfilling the project goals.

The dialog has been initiated with WP4 and WP5 in order to find the optimal solution for transferring the geomechanical and geochemical findings into the simulation model predicting the CO₂ behaviour in the reservoir. It was decided to use geochemical and geomechanical studies to define the operational envelope rather than to directly upscale the findings to the reservoir model.

² PGNIG Krakow: PVT Studies of Reservoir Oil from Zarosice-3 Well (August 2002)

³ In future it might be important to carry out an additional laboratory study on CO₂ – hydrocarbon interactions if the enhanced oil or gas recovery scenarios are selected for piloting and field development.

Study on accounting for geomechanical effects with respect to the dynamic fracture behaviour was started in the reporting period in communication with WP4. The results of Task 4.4 were provided at the end of 2022 (milestone M4.1) and will be analysed in 2023 in combination with the results of the postponed SRT to be performed in Task 3.2.

Task 3.4 – History match of the upgraded reservoir model

Main goal of the history match process is to realize how the reservoir behaved during the production process, and to adjust certain reservoir parameters to improve reservoir description (e.g. based on integration of the results of dynamic data analysis), leading to obtaining acceptable match between observed and simulated data and ensuring prediction capabilities of the reservoir model via proper reservoir description.

History match of the Zar-3 model was initiated immediately after the static reservoir model was transferred from WP2, upscaled and converted into dynamic model. The history match process was started even without having all results from the analysis carried out in Task 3.2 (dynamic data analysis), Task 3.3 (PVT modelling), and inputs from WP4. The goal of such preliminary history match was to use time to get familiar with reservoir behaviour, to understand which reservoir parameters have to be adjusted and to what extent, and evaluate the aquifer size via getting approximately the same pressure support as observed, etc.

Quite a lot of production data from the Zar-3 field is available because the field is relatively young and more modern methods and facilities could be used compared to old fields.

An extremely important source of data for matching reservoir energy and aquifer support is represented by the bottomhole pressure measurements (BHP) in the ZA3 well. That well was producing by pressure depletion without pumping at the beginning, allowing for static and dynamic bottomhole pressure measurements. Later the production was terminated and the well was converted into observation well, so the BHP measurements could continue, which was not possible in other producers that were completed with bottomhole pumps.

Fig. 2.3-5 illustrates real BHP measurements during production history: black circles represent static and yellow circles dynamic BHPs. The black line represents calculated BHP (by a simulator) directly inside the wellbore and the red-brown line represents calculated BHP in the reservoir, nearby the wellbore.

Fig. 2.3-5: Bottomhole pressure development in the ZA3 well: observed values (circles) and values calculated by a simulator (lines).

Several parameters influence the pressure trend during the production history: volume of free gas in the gas cap, volume of solution gas in the oil, volume of oil in the oil zone, volume of water in the aquifer, connectivity throughout the reservoir, presence of communication barriers, etc. Static pressures measured in the ZA3 well indicate important pressure support from the aquifer. BHP declined from approx. 173 to 124 bars after more than 22 years of production, when approx. 470 thousand cubic meters of oil, 52 mil. cubic meters of gas, and 287 thousand cubic meters of water have been produced. If there was weak or no aquifer support, the pressure decline would be much higher.

Almost perfect pressure match was obtained using the following reservoir volumes:

- Gas cap (free gas) = 122 mil. m³
- Solution gas = 65 mil. m³
- Oil = 1 mil. m³
- Water
 - Active grid blocks = 5.4 mil. m³
 - Numerical aquifer = 32 mil. m³

Matching the observed pressures goes hand in hand with matching cumulatively produced volumes of hydrocarbons and water. Relatively good match was also obtained in that parameter, which is clear from Fig. 2.3-6.

Fig. 2.3-6: Cumulatively produced volumes: measured (circles) and calculated by a simulator (lines).

Even if it looks that reasonable history match was obtained, more work still needs to be done especially on the following issues:

- Improving permeability match with values around individual wellbores resulting from dynamic data analysis: For example, the ZA4A well test analysis gives a permeability value of 600 mD for the oil-saturated thickness in 200 m radius around the wellbore but the mean permeability from the history matched model gives value equal to 1,074 mD (Fig. 2.3-7).
- Implementing flow capacity results from the finished dynamic data analysis (Task 3.2) into the model while obtaining acceptable history match at the same time. The results for ZA9AH and ZA3 wells were obtained from Task 3.2 with some delay, and an update of the history match is required to incorporate this input.
- Implementing some results from WP4 into history matching. Handover of WP4 results to WP3 was delayed. Some of the WP4 results are not relevant for the history matching (but important for Task 3.5 and WP8) but, at the same time, some of the WP4 results may have impact on the history matching as well. One of these input parameters to be considered is the pore volume change with pressure, for example.

Fig. 2.3-7: Permeability distribution and the mean value in the current version of the simulation model.

The work carried out on improving the history match and implementing latest results from other Tasks and Work Packages will improve the overall understanding of the reservoir behaviour and enable more precise modelling of reservoir fluids movement, including prediction of CO₂ plume development.

Task 3.5 – Design and simulations of pilot CO₂ injection

History match at certain level and quality was achieved in Task 3.4 (see above). Even though an extensive work is currently ongoing on improving the reservoir characterisation and its better understanding, one simulation scenario of CO₂ injection was simulated to test the stability and robustness of the reservoir model. This scenario contains simulation of a large-scale CO₂ injection. Main goals of this test simulation were:

- Testing the SOLVENT model functionality in the conditions of the Zar-3 field.
- Getting a rough idea about the CO₂ injection process (CO₂ pathways, injection pressures, etc.).
- Obtaining an approximate storage capacity estimate.
- Getting some basic inputs for WP8 to start working on scenarios of future site development.

The scenario chosen for the simulation consists of gas cap depletion after termination of oil production and CO₂ injection into the former gas zone. It was simulated that all the gas from the gas cap was produced only by ZA3 well. This well is believed to be able to produce all the gas due to its top-most position in the gas saturated structure. The currently open well production interval lies in the oil zone, so this was squeezed in the model and the top-most reservoir interval was opened for gas production. The same interval was then also used for CO₂ injection in later phase of the simulation. The CO₂ injection was

terminated when the injected CO₂ reached the spill point. Injection pressure in the injector reached approx. 210 bars, meaning almost 30% overpressurizing above the initial reservoir pressure. That level of overpressurizing must be, however, approved by a geomechanical study. The performed simulation of CO₂ injection indicates that the Zar-3 field could provide a storage capacity of approx. 1.25 mil. tons of CO₂. Extent of the CO₂ plume after injecting this volume of CO₂ is illustrated in Fig. 2.3-8.

Fig. 2.3-8: CO₂ plume extension (orange colour) after injecting 1.25 Mt of CO₂.

Deviations and changes

The work in WP3 experienced some delays in 2022. The analysis of dynamic data at NORCE in Task 3.2 was finished later than planned and its final results still have to be incorporated in the history matching process.

The step-rate test initially planned in Task 3.2 for autumn 2021 and postponed to June 2022 had to be delayed again. The reason was an unexpected presence of a barrier inside the wellbore that disables equipping the borehole with a BHP gauge. The situation requires a technical well intervention, the time planning of which is dependent on the availability of the maintenance rig and spare fibreglass tubing (currently unavailable on the market). Unfortunately, both factors are beyond the remit of the consortium. The current (confirmed) plan is to perform the test in mid-2023, which will still allow for incorporating the test results in WP3 outcomes. It needs to be stressed that execution of the SRT is not critical for the achievement of WP3 objectives but influences the level of the dynamic modelling uncertainty.

Task 3.3 experienced delays especially in upscaling of geomechanical effects, which were caused by delayed achievement of Milestone M4.1 “Geomechanical constraints of the injection programme handed over from W4 to WP3”. The main reason here is the

paternity leave of WP4 Work Package leader in the first half of 2022 that held up the work in WP4.

The history match in Task 3.4 has been achieved at a certain quality level , but more work in 2023 is still needed to improve the permeability match with values resulting from the dynamic data analysis and conditioning the reservoir model to estimated flow capacities per wells and the results from WP4 (geomechanics).

Thus, the corresponding Milestone M3.2 planned for August 2022 has not been achieved because the work on the history match is still ongoing. It is expected that the Milestone will be achieved in early 2023.

In general, the work in WP3 is behind schedule in several Tasks. There is, however, a good chance to make up most of the delays in the first half of 2023, without jeopardizing achievement of the planned WP objectives.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

No results were planned for this reporting period.

Milestones

Milestone	Date	Description
M3.1	achieved 03/2022	Transfer of upscaled geological model from WP2
M3.2	Not achieved, (planned 08/2022)	Transfer of history matched reservoir model upgraded to be capable of simulating CO2 injection scenarios to WP8

2.4 WORK PACKAGE 4 – Geomechanical characteristics

Summary

The objective of WP4 is to characterize geomechanical properties of the storage complex and assess how CO₂ injection impacts the reservoir and the storage complex from geomechanical point of view. The aim is to ensure mechanical reservoir stability during the whole storage site lifecycle. Geomechanical laboratory tests in context with the principal reservoir stresses represent the basis of the used methodology. The influence of CO₂ on the geomechanical stiffness and strength has been evaluated, as well as the effects of re-pressurization and cooling caused by injecting cold CO₂ on the effective stress field. The impact of uncertainty was included via Monte Carlo simulations. This work has been conducted to qualify the safe operation window in the planned injection scenario of the Zar-3 CO₂ storage pilot. The work in 2022 generally ran according to the plan, with slight delays in some of the Tasks. The work package has been led by NORCE; the experimental work was performed by VSB. Both partners collaborated on assessment and interpretation of results and preparing the reports with support by MND. Both planned results (R4.2 and R4.3) were delivered and the scheduled milestone M4.1 has been achieved.

Task 4.1 – Geomechanical parameter determination of overburden and reservoir samples

The objective of this Task was to perform the rock mechanical stiffness and strength tests for geomechanical assessment of the relevant formations in the reservoir complex. The cylindrical core samples, that were subject to mechanical tests, were acquired from the core storage repository by MND (see an overview in Tab. 2.4-1). The experimental work was performed by VSB and has been completed as planned within the limits of the interim report period. Result R4.2 (Report on geomechanical data to be stored in the project database) describes in detail the methods used and results obtained in this Task. The envelope that determines the rock mechanical strength was obtained via:

- Brazilian tests for tensile strength;
- Triaxial tests, where axial stress was loaded until failure with a side stress at 7 and 15 MPa;
- Unconfined compressive strength tests (UCS) performed with axial failure without any side support;
- Hydrostatic confining pressure cycling to determine the relation between confining stress and porosity and permeability, and to evaluate if reservoir pore pressure depletion down to 2 MPa will lead to compaction failure.

Tab. 2.4-1: Overview of numbers of rock samples used in the geomechanical test program for six different lithostratigraphic units represented in the Zar-3 storage complex.

Age	Lithostratigraphy	Type	Number of rock samples
Upper Jurassic	Mikulov Fm.	Seal	9
Paleogene	Žarošice Mb.	Seal	9
Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm. - nearby field	Reservoir - possible analogue	1
Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm. (Nikolčice Fm.)	Reservoir	1
Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	50
Lower Carboniferous	Myslejovice Fm.	Side seal	8

The strengths were compiled into failure envelopes that quantify the stresses, at which irreversible rock failure may occur. All test results are reported in R4.2, and an example of a failure envelope in *qp*-space is displayed in Fig. 2.4-1.

In total, 23 Brazilian tests, 4 triaxial test, 8 unconfined stress tests, and 21 hydrostatic confining pressure cycle tests were executed in VSB labs. All geomechanical tests results are summarized in Attachment “WP4-MASTER_Results_CO2SPICER.xls” to the result R4.2 and will be uploaded to project geodatabase in early 2023.

Fig. 2.4-1: Combined figure of tensile strength (green), shear failure (dashed) and the re-opening of eventual pre-existing fractures, displayed in *qp*-space.

Task 4.2 – Non-destructive determination of mechanical changes for samples exposed to CO₂

All rock samples used in the geomechanical Work Package were subject to ultrasonic sound velocity determination prior to testing. In total 73 measurements were performed. These tests do not destroy the rock samples. The corresponding measurements of the

primary and secondary/shear wave velocities were used to determine the dynamic elastic Young’s modulus and Poisson’s ratio.

Part of the results is shown in Fig. 2.4-2 where the relation between the estimated dynamic Young’s modulus and measured porosity is displayed (porosity was only measured on 15 of these samples.). The Reuss lower bound⁴ was fitted to the data (orange line). This orange curve was extrapolated to 10 % porosity and the stiffness at this value yielded 6.25 GPa (green line). A histogram of dynamic Young’s modulus values is shown in (2.4-3).

Fig. 2.4-2: Derived Young’s modulus from measurements of v_s and v_p on the rock samples.

Fig. 2.4-3: Histogram of dynamic Young’s modulus values calculated from ultrasonic measurements for all tests.

⁴ Reuss lower bound for rock stiffness (K_{fr}) as function of porosity (ϕ) is given by $\frac{1}{K_{fr}} = \frac{\phi}{K_f} + \frac{1-\phi}{K_s}$, where K_f is the fluid stiffness (water), and K_s is the solid/mineral stiffness. The porosity was allowed to vary between 1% and 35% (i.e. at 1% K_s was used and at 45% porosity K_f was used).

Fig. 2.4-4: Correlation between tensile strength (T_0) of all tested samples and the associated dynamic Young's modulus estimated from ultrasonic measurements of v_p and v_s . Reservoir rock samples are plotted in blue circles and seals in orange. Reducing Young's modulus by 34% reduces T_0 by 11%. Seals are stronger than reservoir rocks.

Fig. 2.4-5: Correlation between results of unconfined compressive strength (UCS) measurements and the dynamic Young's modulus estimated from ultrasonic measurements. The arrow shows the reduction in stiffness caused by exposure of the rock to CO_2 (reduction to 66% of the value before exposure to CO_2 leads to a corresponding reduction in UCS). Reservoir rocks are displayed in blue circles, while the seals in orange.

The data sets acquired in Tasks 4.1 and 4.2 were used to determine correlations between the dynamic stiffnesses (from Task 4.2) and corresponding rock mechanical strengths (from Task 4.1). Thus, measurement pairs of dynamic Young's modulus and strengths on the exactly same samples could be used to establish correlations. The dynamic Young's modulus correlated with tensile strength is displayed in Fig. 2.4-4, Young's modulus and

UCS in Fig. 2.4-5, and Young's modulus and axial stress at failure (s_1) for triaxial tests in Fig. 2.4-6.

Fig. 2.4-6: Correlation between ultrasonic dynamic stiffness (Young's modulus) and measured axial principal strength in triaxial tests. The side stress was kept at 7 MPa and the sample was loaded axially to failure; the stress s_1 is plotted along y-axis. The arrow shows the reduction in the elastic modulus caused by exposure of the rock to CO_2 (reduction to 66% of the initial value leads to a corresponding reduction in the value of s_1).

How does exposure of CO_2 lead to strength changes? The laboratory strength tests destroy each sample. As such, there is no direct way to determine experimentally how prolonged exposure to CO_2 at in-situ conditions leads to strength changes. Due to this, to get insights into the geomechanical changes by geochemical alterations, we estimated dynamic stiffnesses from ultrasonic stiffness measurements (non-destructive) before and after each sample was exposed to CO_2 in reaction chambers for six months at in-situ conditions. Five samples were tested before and after CO_2 exposure (see Tab. 2.4-2).

Tab. 2.4-2: Dynamic elastic modulus from sound velocity before and after 6 months of CO_2 exposure. For the three samples from the Za-3 reservoir, the Young's modulus decreased to 53, 56 and 90% (average 66%) of values before exposure.

Sample ID	Age	Lithostratigraphy	Type	Before				After CO ₂ exposure				Change Youngs mod.
				Vp, km/s	Vs, km/s	nu, 1	E, GPa	Vp, km/s	Vs, km/s	nu, 1	E, GPa	
UH11_c4_b3_d	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm. - nearby field	Reservoir - possible analogue	6.67	2.28	0.43	32.71	6.09	2.87	0.36	49.23	151 %
ZA3_c1_b3_a	Paleogene	Žarošice Mb.	Seal	5.68	3.31	0.24	59.83	5.69	2.92	0.32	49.53	83 %
ZA6A_c1_b4_c	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.79	2.45	0.32	41.22	3.35	1.80	0.30	21.77	53 %
ZA4A_c3_b3_c	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.11	0.82	0.41	4.93	1.86	0.61	0.44	2.77	56 %
ZA4A_c4_b2_b	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm. (Nikolčice Fm.)	Reservoir	3.14	1.64	0.31	17.70	2.65	1.63	0.19	15.93	90 %

In the three reservoir samples where CO₂ and brine could react also inside each sample (not subject to control by the transport of reactive elements), an average reduction in Young's modulus to 66% of the value before exposure was observed. We used the correlations in Figs. 2.4-4 to 2.4-6 (black arrows) to quantify how this reduction by 34% in Young's modulus corresponds to strength changes. Our estimates suggest the tensile strength is reduced by 11% (i.e. to 89% of its value before exposure), UCS is reduced by 39 % (61 % of the original value), and the principal stress from the tri-axial test is reduced by 24% (76% of the value before).

When reporting this data in the upcoming peer-reviewed articles, a more detailed statistical analysis method is needed. The data is scattered, and we have a very limited number of data points. Thus, when testing a hypothesis based on the reported data set, we will use hypothesis testing methods to convey inherent uncertainty into the reported conclusions (with uncertainty error bands).

Task 4.3 – Field stress and strength determination at in-situ conditions, and the effect of cooling

The main objective of this Task was to identify the safe operation window for CO₂ injection from geomechanical perspective. Increased pore pressure reduces the effective stress, and cooling leads to thermal contraction that reduces the horizontal stress, although the vertical stress remains the same in weight dominated systems. Further, as described in Task 4.2, the reservoir rocks seem to weaken when exposed to CO₂ at in-situ conditions.

As outlined in the Task 4.1, the mechanical strengths of rocks were evaluated and plotted with invariant stresses at each axis (making the results applicable to any stress geometry).

Rock mechanical measurements are only useful in this context when put in context with the Earth stresses in the field. During this reporting period we intensified the work to identify what these stresses are. There are no reported stress tests in the field, and since the well injection tests were postponed (see WP3), our estimates of stresses relied on the application of three methods:

1. Extrapolation from nearby fields
2. Break out analysis
3. Calculation of vertical stress from density logs (weight of overburden) and determination of side stress via Poisson's ratio (measured)

The principal stresses that we obtained are displayed in Fig. 2.4-7. The method and results are documented in the data sheet "WP4-Stress_database_CO2SPICER.xls", attached to result R4.2.

Fig. 2.4-7: Field stresses at 1724 m depth. Extrapolated values (squares) from measurements at three localities east of Ostrava (140 km away). The values calculated from vertical weight and Poisson's ratio are displayed as diamonds.

The corresponding stresses used in the analysis of stability are shown in Tab. 2.4-3. The value chosen for the uncertainty analysis (in Task 4.4) is displayed in bold.

Tab. 2.4-3: Estimated and extrapolated largest and least earth stress for the reservoir. The value chosen in the uncertainty analysis is shown.

	s_1 [MPa]	s_3 [MPa]	P_f [MPa] (hydrostat)
Overburden and uni-axial strain	38.9 ± 0.8	20.0 ± 0.6	17.2 ± 1
Extrapolation of nearby fields	42.3 ± 0.8	22.9 ± 1.9	17.2 ± 1
Chosen for the analysis	40 ± 1.0	22 ± 2	17.2 ± 1

When assessing how the injection of cold CO₂ into the rock masses changes mechanical stability, it is useful to consider this via invariant stresses that remain the same for all coordinate systems. The Earth stresses (s_1 and s_3) and pore pressure (P_f) represent a point in in qp -space defined by:

$$q = s_1 - s_3$$

$$p = \frac{s_1 + s_3}{2} - \alpha_B P_f$$

The Biot coefficient is given by α_B (measured in the lab). As can be seen, increasing pore pressure does not change q , but it reduces the value of p . Correspondingly, cooling of the reservoir when its lateral size is constant leads to a reduction in s_3 . Reducing s_3 reduces

p and increases q , moving the stress in qp -space towards the failure line. A 2D assessment is conservative, assuming the intermediate stress $s_2 = s_3$.

When estimating how much the side stress is reduced, this can be calculated in weight dominated systems (s_1 is vertical and remains the same irrespectively of temperature; thus, the cooling and subsequent thermal contraction lead to a reduction in the side stress). The thermoelastic coupling coefficient relates changes in temperature (ΔT) to side stress changes (Δs_3). At uni-axial strain conditions this is expressed as:

$$\Delta s_3 = \frac{E \alpha_T}{1 - \nu} \Delta T$$

Here, the Young's modulus (E) and Poisson's ratio (ν) were estimated from the sound velocity tests. The thermal expansion coefficient (α_T) has been measured on four samples (two of which were reservoir rocks) and compared to values reported in the literature. The measured values vary significantly because of experimental uncertainty and geologic variability. As such, based on this variability, upper and lower bounds have been established as displayed in Tab. 2.4-4. As can be seen from the coupling coefficient, a reduction in reservoir temperature by 1°C leads to a reduction in horizontal stress by 0.4 to 1.8 bar. The errors are large, because of inherent experimental variability in the results.

Tab. 2.4-4: Thermoelastic coupling coefficient from upper and lower bounds of the thermal expansion coefficient, Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio.

	Lower	Upper	Average	Delta
Thermal expansion coeff., K ⁻¹	1.00E-05	1.80E-05	1.40E-05	4.00E-06
Young's modulus, MPa	3.00E+03	6.25E+03	4.63E+03	1.63E+03
Poisson's ratio	0.300	0.400	0.350	0.050
Thermoelastic coupling coeff. [MPaK⁻¹]	0.043	0.188	0.115	0.072

The experimental work has been concluded, and the results are on their way to be interpreted, provided for further use in WP3 and WP8 and written up in peer-reviewed publications according to the further work plan.

Task 4.4 – Uncertain input data leading to probabilistic faulting and fracturing estimate – maximal CO₂ injection pressure determination

There is inherent variability in the results obtained from the laboratory analyses that originates both from geological variability and accuracy of the test methods and estimates. Further on, the Earth stresses are subject to great uncertainty. The advantage of analysing rock mechanical failure envelopes in qp -space is that the earth stresses are represented as dots, instead of circles as in $\tau\sigma$ -space. This simplifies the mechanical stability assessment for each statistical realization.

Monte Carlo analysis tools were used to evaluate the mechanical stability of each sample when drawn from a uniform distribution of stresses and rock mechanical data set. The corresponding data sheet - Excel file "WP4_QP-error-FailureEnvelope.xls" - is attached to both the result R4.3 and the Milestone M4.1, and will be uploaded to the geodatabase. The results are shown in Fig. 2.4-8. Each dot represents one realization and its position relative to the failure envelopes can therefore be evaluated. The figure displays three

failure mechanisms: (a) shear failure envelope (black dashed line) combined from UCS and triaxial test results, (b) tensile strength tests results (green line), and (c) re-opening of pre-existing fractures with their surface normal to the direction of s_3 (orange line). The initial, pristine pore pressures at 55°C temperature are shown in the green circles, and the impact of re-pressurization (grey), cooling (blue) and combined effect (yellow) is displayed, respectively. For each case the number of instances where the stress exceeds any of the failure lines can be counted to determine the probability of failure.

Fig. 2.4-8: Plot of a series of stresses drawn from uniform distribution. The effect of cooling and re-pressurization is displayed.

This analysis was done for a range of reservoir temperatures and pressures, and rock failure probabilities were calculated for various cases (Fig. 2.4-9).

Fig. 2.4-9: Probability of rock failure as function of reservoir fluid pressure and temperature. The impact on intact rocks is displayed on the left and the re-opening of pre-existing fractures on the right.

The outcomes of the work in Tasks 4.2-4.4 are summarized in result R4.3 “Development of stress magnitude and strengths in different cases (side stress reduction by cooling and modifications in strengths by CO₂)” that was submitted in December 2022 and is attached to the Interim Report.

The accompanying Excel data sheets that compile all the quantitative results of the work conducted in WP4 were uploaded to the project geodatabase:

- Field stress evaluation: “WP4-Stress_database_CO2SPICER.xls”
- Data from geomechanical lab tests: “WP4-MASTER_Results_CO2SPICER.xls”
- Monte Carlo simulation using Excel: “WP4_QP-error-FailureEnvelope.xls”

In addition, extensive documentation summarizing geomechanical input in dynamic modelling was prepared to support achievement of milestone “M4.1 – Geomechanical constraints in the injection programme handed over to WP3”.

Deviations and changes

There were no major deviations in WP4 that would exceed the time frame of the interim report. Some delay was encountered in Tasks 4.3 and 4.4. Result R4.3 was completed with a delay of 4 months, and milestone M4.1 was achieved 6 months later than planned. This has slightly affected the work progress in WP3.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

Other results		
No.	Result title	Date of submission
R4.2	Report on geomechanical data to be stored in the project Geodatabase	03/2022, updated version 12/2022
R4.3	Report describing development of stresses magnitude and strengths in different cases (side stress by cooling and modifications in strengths by CO ₂)	12/2022

Milestones

Milestone	Date	Description
M4.1	achieved 12/2022	Geomechanical constraints on the injection program handed over to WP3

2.5 WORK PACKAGE 5 – Geochemistry of rocks and fluids

Summary

The main objective of Work Package 5 is to gain knowledge about composition and properties of formation fluids (i.e. oil, gas and water), injection fluids, reservoir rocks, and caprock. In 2022 the analytical works were performed according to the plan by CGS (WP leader) in close cooperation with VSB, MND and NORCE.

Task 5.1 – Geochemistry of fluids

In addition to the oil, water and gas samples collected at Zar-3 in June and November 2021, two new oil+water+gas samples were collected on 17 May 2022. Analyses of the new and archival oil samples were completed using the gas chromatography GC-FID and GC-MS methods.

Geochemistry of oils

Analyses of oil molecular composition were performed in CGS labs in 2022 on oil samples from wells selected by MND from broader Zar-3 field area and neighbouring oil fields (Tab. 2.5-1). The analytical data are stored in the project geodatabase.

Tab. 2.5-1: Overview of oil samples provided by MND from broader Zar-3 field area where molecular organic geochemical analyses were performed by CGS in 2022.

Sample No.	Sample No. MND	Field name	Well No.
1	3163	Borkovany	1
2	3164	Borkovany	2
3	3165	Borkovany	3
4	3166	Borkovany	4
5	3167	Borkovany	101
6	3168	Bošovice	4
7	3169	Bošovice	103
8	3170	Uhřice	22
9	3171	Uhřice	34
10	3172	Uhřice	49
11	3173	Uhřice	57
12	3174	Uhřice	64
13	3175	Uhřice	78A
14	3176	Uhřice	86
15	3177	Uhřice	102
16	3178	Žarošice	4A
17	3179	Hostěrádky	102A
18	3180	Otnice	101

Based on the density, viscosity, acid values and other properties of the oils in the area given in Tab. 2.5-1, the Zar-3 oil is classified as medium sweet crude oil. Based on the chromatographic molecular analysis of the Zar-3 oil (from well ZA4A) is composed of a heavily biodegraded black oil (C₁₅₊) with almost no n-alkanes (on PM scale >6), with a non-biodegraded gasoline range light oil of later migration event. The analytical data will be further processed in 2023 and correlations will be evaluated in order to provide the probable migration pathways of oils in the region.

Geochemistry of formation water

Chemical analyses of formation water samples from Za-3 were completed in CGS, VSB and MND labs. The results are shown in Table 2.5-2. Complete analytical results are stored in the project geodatabase. The data serve as a basis for the CO₂-rock-water interaction experiments (Task 5.4) and modelling (Task 5.5), as well as for the reservoir modelling (WP3).

Tab. 2.5-2: Chemical composition of formation waters from the Zar-3 field.

Za-well#	Depth m	Sampling date	Depth 2 m	Density at 15°C g/cm ³	pH	Electrical conductivity at 25°C mS/cm
4A	1802.3	21.3.2012	2842		7.09	36.0
5H	2550.2	2015	2860	1.0177	7.25	36.0
8AH	2338.0	10.4.2015	2440	1.0178	8.43	37.5
8AH	2338.0	2.6.2016	2440		7.25	38.3

Za-well#	Depth m	Ammonium ion NH ₄ mg/l	Chloride Cl mg/l	Iodine I mg/l	Bromine Br mg/l	Acid- neutralizing capacity-4,5 mmol/l
4A	1802.3	<1.30	12000	68	77	
5H	2550.2	31.4	12700	51	71	40.7
8AH	2338.0	13.0	12200	68	83	
8AH	2338.0	32.4	11700	68	230	30.8

Za-well#	Depth m	Bicarbona- tes HCO ₃ mg/l	Sulfates SO ₄ mg/l	Magnesium Mg mg/l	Calcium Ca mg/l	Total hardness mmol/l	Total dissolved solids TDS mg/l
4A	1802.3	2800	866	96.0	401	27.9	25170
5H	2550.2	2480	1130	137	116	8.53	26130
8AH	2338.0	2150		135	22.5	6.11	24230
8AH	2338.0	1880	1410	133	440	16.5	24450

Za-well#	Depth m	Ba mg/l	Fe mg/l	Mn mg/l	Li mg/l	Rb mg/l	Sr mg/l	Na mg/l	K mg/l	(S ²⁻) mg/l	H ₂ SiO ₃ mg/l	HBO ₂ mg/l
4A	1802.3	1.04	16.9	-	2.90	0.28	26.2	8200	411		11.6	197
5H	2550.2	<2.50	1.34	-	3.36	0.35	23.0	8890	271		42.3	179
8AH	2338.0	<0.50	18.8	-	3.17		6.23	8710	482		32.5	305
8AH	2338.0	<2.50	14.9	0.42	3.29	0.52	26.1	8070	473	<0.2	31.5	231

Results of the analyses shown in Figs. 2.5-1 and 2.5-2 show that the formation water in Zar-3 field is a typical marine, deeply buried water of Na – Cl type and low HCO₃⁻ content.

Fig. 2.5-1: Geochemistry of formation waters from Zar-3 and neighbouring fields shown in Piper's diagram.

Fig. 2.5-2 Geochemistry the formation waters from Zar-3 and neighbouring fields shown in “Burov” diagram.

Gas geochemistry

Eleven gas samples from 7 wells at Zar-3 were analysed for chemical composition (Tabs. 2.5-3 and 2.5-4).

Tab. 2.5-3: List of wells and intervals with produced gas in the Zar-3 field.

No.	Za-well #	Depth 1 (m)	Depth 2 (m)
1	3	1740	1780
2	3	1740	1780
3	4A	1802	1842
4	4A	1802	1842
5	4A	1802	1842
6	5H	2550	2860
7	6A	1899	2000
8	8AH	2338	2440
9	8AH	2338	2440
10	9AH	2202	2475
11	14H	2117	2255

In 2022, isotopic composition of carbon $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and deuterium δD was measured in 8 gas samples (Tab. 2.5-4). The first two samples were collected after a break in production and represent stratified gas accumulated in the uppermost part of the annulus. The following ZA4A sample was collected after a 5-min vent and is interpreted as representative of the gas exsolved from the oil in reservoir.

Tab. 2.5-4: Chemical and isotopic composition of gases in the Zar-3 field.

Sample No.	2130404	2130405	2130489	2130490	2130491	2130492	2140685	2220146
Well name & number	ZA4a tub_1	ZA4a tub_2	ZA4A anu_3	ZA4A anu_4	ZA14H anu_1	ZA14H anu_2	ZA4a tub_3	ZA8AH tub_1
Sampling date	28.07.21	28.07.21	05.11.21	05.11.21	05.11.21	05.11.21	02.12.21	17.05.22
CO ₂ % _{vol}	2.0	1.9	4.9	5.2	5.7	5.8	21.5	1.4
$\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ (‰)	11.8	7.6	9.3	8.5	11.2	10.4	16.2	6.9
St. dev. (‰)	0.1	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2
CH ₄ % _{vol}	34.3	33.9	89.5	89.3	89.3	89.3	50.6	89.9
$\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ (‰)	-17.5	-17.6	-37.3	-38.2	-39.0	-38.6	-37.2	-37.9
St. dev. (‰)	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.2
ethane % _{vol}	2.4	3.4	4.4	4.2	3.4	3.7	11.5	3.9
$\delta^{13}\text{C-C}_2\text{H}_6$ (‰)	-18.8	-18.5	-23.7	-23.8	-23.8	-23.9	-23.8	-23.6
St. dev. (‰)	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.3
propane % _{vol}			0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	1.7	0.5
$\delta^{13}\text{C-C}_3\text{H}_8$ (‰)			-19.0	-19.2	-19.6	-19.4	-19.6	-21.1
St. dev. (‰)			0.0	0.1	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.1
isobutane % _{vol}								0.154
$\delta^{13}\text{C-i-but.}$ (‰)								-25.1
n-butane % _{vol}								0.1
$\delta^{13}\text{C-n-but.}$ (‰)								-22.6
hydrogen % _{vol}								
$\delta\text{D-CH}_4$ (‰)							-188.2	-179.0
St. dev. (‰)							1,66	2,0

According to the chemical and isotopic composition (Tab. 2.5-4) of the gases from the Zar-3 field, the reservoir gas is a typical oil-associated gas of thermogenic origin. H₂S was not detected in the initial production history. During the more recent years, traces of H₂S occurred, probably due to the activity of sulphate-reducing bacteria associated with reinjection of the produced water back into the reservoir.

Task 5.2 – Microbial activity in the reservoir

The DNA analysis of the water sample taken in 2021 from the production well ZA4A, depth ca. 1800 m TVDSS, was completed and 28 families of Archaea and Bacteria were identified (Figs. 2.5-3 and 2.5-4).

Fig. 2.5-3: Results of microbiological analysis of a formation water sample from the ZA4A production well. The size of each box represents relative proportion of the monitored microbiological class.

Both Archaea (primitive bacteria) and Bacteria were found to be present in the Zar-3 reservoir. Sulfur reducing Bacteria are absolutely dominant in the water (Desulfobulbia, Desulfobacteria, Campylobacteria), coupled with oxidation of organic compounds from the oil. Hydrogen sulfate (H₂S), pyrite and CO₂ are the products of the sulfate reduction process. The process is much more energetically favourable than methanogenesis, which is rather suppressed in Zar-3.

Clostridia, Bacilli and Proteobacteria make another functional group on the site. These anaerobic or facultative anaerobic organisms break down larger organic compound through some fermentative or respiratory processes and produce smaller organic molecules, e.g. acetates, which may serve as food for the Methanomicrobia.

Fig. 2.5-4: Cluster analysis of genom information for the same sample as in Fig. 2.5-3: Colours show relative abundance (RA) of individual families in formation water in direct contact with oil.

Among Archaea, Thermococci prevail together with thermophilic or hyper-thermophilic degraders of organic matter in oil and sediments. They produce smaller organic molecules, which may serve as food for methanogens (Methanomicrobia) and ammonia oxidizers. Thermococci and Methanomicrobia occur, however, in lower quantity.

Ammonia oxidizers were also found in low numbers.

The microbiological picture of the Zar-3 site is similar to some examples described in the literature (e.g. Kotlar et al. 2011⁵, Kirk et al. 2016⁶), with sulfates-reducing organisms dominating the sample. Availability of sulfates is controlled by the host rock geochemistry. Undesirable formation of H₂S may be suppressed by nitrate addition to the injection water (Zhou et al. 2020⁷). It should be mentioned, that using chemicals, such as nitrates or bacteriocides, to fight against H₂S also suppresses methanogenesis. The probability of throat clogging by growth of bacterial biomass and enhanced microbial methanogenesis will be dealt with in 2023.

Task 5.3 – Geochemistry and mineralogy of rocks

In 2022, additional 21 core samples (example in Fig. 2.5-5) were analysed for chemical composition using elemental analysis of organic and inorganic carbon (TOC, TIC and calculated calcite or dolomite), x-ray fluorescence (XRF) and mineral composition by x-ray diffraction (XRD, Fig. 2.5-6). The results were uploaded to project geodatabase.

⁵ Kotlar, H.K. et al. (2011): High coverage sequencing of DNA from microorganisms living in an oil reservoir 2.5 kilometres subsurface. *Environmental Microbiology Reports* 3(6), 674–681

⁶ Kirk, M.F. et al. (2016): Interplay between microorganisms and geochemistry in geological carbon storage. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, Vol. 47, pp. 386-395

⁷ Zhou, L. et al. (2020): Functional microorganisms involved in the sulfur and nitrogen metabolism in production water from a high-temperature offshore petroleum reservoir. *International Biodeterioration & Biodegradation*, Vol. 154, 105057

The available core samples from deep wells at the Zar-3 represent only a limited depth interval. To characterize the entire profile of the Zar-3 reservoir, drill cuttings were provided by MND in December 2022. Geochemical and mineralogical analyses are planned for the project phase 2023.

Fig. 2.5-5: New core samples of caprocks used for geochemical and geomechanical tests: Paleogene Nesvačilka Fm., Žarošice Mb. (ZA4A_1866 m_c1_b5) and Lower Carboniferous of the Myslejovice Fm. (ZA3_1886 m_c6_b4).

Fig. 2.5-6: Ternary plot of dolomite, calcite, and chlorite + quartz + feldspar (Cl+Q+Fsp) of rock samples from the selected lithostratigraphic units of the Zar-3 storage complex: Paleogene (Pg) of the Žarošice Mb., Upper Jurassic (J3) of the Mikulov, Vranovice, and Nikolčice Formations., Lower Carboniferous (C1) of the Myslejovice Fm. The numbers in legend indicate 1 – lower, 3 – upper chronostratigraphic unit. New data points for the caprocks are included.

Vranovice Fm., the principal reservoir, represents an end member lithology of almost pure dolomite and iron-rich dolomite. The Nikolčice Fm., which underlies the Vranovice Fm., is rich in dolomite but has also quartz and minor rock-building minerals, such as

feldspars. The underlying Carboniferous Myslejovice Fm. is composed of almost pure siliciclastic rocks (shale, siltstone and sandstone). Overlying marls of the Mikulov Fm. show broad variety of mineral composition, little or minor dolomite, abundant calcite, siliciclastics, mainly clay minerals, and pyrite. Paleogene siltstones of the Nesvačilka Fm. are rich in pyrite and have variable carbonate content. The results will be used, among others, for optimization of the experimental conditions of the fluid – rock interactions (Task 5.4).

Fig. 2.5-7: Photomicrographs of the Vranovice Fm. rock sample (well ZA3, md 1595.5 m, TVDSS 1375.90 m) shows cavernous dolostone - planar-s dolomite (A, B, C, E – PPL), with coarser pore lining saddle/cement dolomite (sd), zonal in fluorescence (D, F), and recrystallized or leached bioclasts. Porosity is of vuggy and moldic type. Gas porosity is 2,65 %.

Additional microscopic investigations of thin sections, performed at CGS in 2022, provided valuable details of lithology, depositional environment and diagenesis (Figs. 2.5-7 and 2.5-8).

Fig. 2.5-8: Photomicrographs of the caprock of the Nesvačilka Fm. (well ZA3, md 1460 m, TVDSS 1237 m): A, B, C, E – PPL, D, F – fluorescent light. Dolomitic sandstone to arkose with quartz (q), feldspar, intraclasts and bioclasts. Some grains are surrounded by micrite envelope and isopachous calcite cement. Space between grains is almost completely cemented. Some of the interparticle and moldic pores (p) are still open (stained by blue epoxy resin).

A thin sections atlas of photomicrographs of the reservoir rocks and caprocks with interpretations of petrography, depositional facies and diagenesis was put together; the results were uploaded to the geodatabase and made available to all project partners for further use, primarily in the rock type distribution in the dynamic model.

Optical porosity

Photomicrographs of 26 rock samples impregnated by blue epoxy resin were analysed using image analysis. The relative area of open pores in a selected thin section area corresponds to optical porosity. The interpreted pore size distributions suggest an important contribution of cavernous and fracture pores with diameter ranging from 100 to 300 μm to the reservoir total porosity. The caprocks have about 5-10 times lower

porosity than the reservoir rocks and have the majority of pores in the clay size (<5 μm) diameter (Fig. 2.5-9).

Fig. 2.5-9: Optical porosity results: pore size distribution in reservoir rock (Vranovice Fm.) and caprocks (Mikulov and Nesvačilka Fms.).

Task 5.4 – Experiments on CO₂ – rock – fluid interactions and a predictive model

First CO₂-brine-rock experiments in the reaction chamber were carried out in 2022 at VSB. Experiments started on 10 January 2022. Five dolomite samples (reservoir rocks) from the Zar-3 field were used.

Four cells in the reaction chamber were used for the CO₂-water-rock experiments. Details of used rock samples are given in Tabs. 2.5-5 and 2.5-6, together with exposure time in months.

Tab. 2.5-5: Samples used for CO₂-fluid-rock experiments in VSB laboratory.

No	Well name # core_box_cm1_cm2	Sample Measured depth (m)	Sample TVDSS (m)	Chrono-stratigraphy	Lithostratigraphic formation	Duration of test (months)
1	UH11_4_3_61_77	1421.61	1167.34	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	6
2	ZA3_3_4_51_61	1599.01	1375.90	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	1, 3, 6
3	ZA4A_3_3_29_44	1789.29	1530.91	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	3, 6
4	ZA4A_4_2_60_85	1831.60	1573.21	Middle Jurassic	Nikolčice Fm.	1, 3, 4, 6
5	ZA6A_1_4_70_85	1932.70	1566.14	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	1, 3, 4, 6

 Tab. 2.5-6: Sample batch weights used for CO₂-fluid-rock experiments.

No	Well name # core_box_cm1_cm2	1 month batch (g)	3 months batch (g)	4 months batch (g)	6 months batch (g)
1	UH-11_4_3_61_77	-	-	-	28.92
2	ZA3_3_4_51_61	6.46	9.57	-	70.82
3	ZA4A_3_3_29_44	-	35.89	-	255.00
4	ZA4A_4_2_60_85	10.72	11.87	66.11	115.47
5	ZA6A_1_4_70_85	10.46	12.65	13.74	18.28

Samples were placed to cells of the reaction chamber and flooded with formation water (brine). Pressure and temperature for the experimental process were set at 15 MPa and 53°C, which corresponds to the estimated injection pressure in the Zar-3 storage, and to the reservoir temperature, respectively.

Formation water used in the experiments was collected from the ZA4A well as a suspension of oil with water. Oil was removed from the large sample. Water has a brine character, i.e. is strongly mineralized, sodium-chloride geochemical type. The chemical composition of the brine measured in MND laboratories is shown in Tab. 2.5-7.

Tab. 2.5-7: Chemical analysis of the ZA4A formation water (MND laboratories).

Parameter	Unit	Value	Method identification	Unc.
Density at 15°C	g/cm ³	1,0173	SOP 18/01	±0,1%
pH		7,07	SOP 02/01	±2%
Electrical conductivity at 25°C	mS/cm	36,5	SOP 03/01	±3%
Ammonium NH ₄ ⁺	mg/l	32,6	SOP 08/01, part B	±10%
Chloride Cl	mg/l	12300	SOP 22/02, part A	±10%
Iodide I	mg/l	43	PN 22	* ±10%
Bromide Br	mg/l	54	PN 23	* ±15%
Acid neutralizing capacity ANC-4,5	mmol/l	42,3	SOP 14/01	±5%
Bicarbonate HCO ₃	mg/l	2580	SOP 14/01	±10%
Sulphate SO ₄	mg/l	535	SOP 09/01	±10%
Calcium Ca	mg/l	111	SOP 12/01, part A	±10%
Magnesium Mg	mg/l	107	SOP 12/01, part B	±10%
Hardness total	mmol/l	7,16	SOP 12/01, part B	±10%
Mineralization	mg/l	24590	SOP 22/02, part A	±10%
Baryum Ba	mg/l	<2,50	SOP 16/01, part A	
Iron Fe	mg/l	0,353	SOP 16/01, part A	±10%
Mangane Mn	mg/l	<0,010	SOP 16/01, part A	
Lithium Li	mg/l	3,17	SOP 16/01, part A	±10%
Rubidium Rb	mg/l	0,270	SOP 16/01, part A	±10%
Strontium Sr	mg/l	19,2	SOP 16/01, part A	±15%
Sodium Na	mg/l	8570	SOP 16/01, part A	±10%
Potassium K	mg/l	252	SOP 16/01, part A	±10%
Sulfide sulfur S(-II)	mg/l	23,7	PN 26	* ±20%
Silicate H ₂ SiO ₃	mg/l	40	PN 25	* ±20%
Boric acid HBO ₂	mg/l	175	PN 24	* ±20%

Post-experiment water samples were taken after 1, 3, 4 and 6 months. Analyses were done in the VSB laboratory. The brine samples were hydrochemically classified as sodium-chloride type. Genetic classification corresponds to marine and deeply buried formation waters. Long-term interaction with injected CO₂ has not changed the brine character. The results are displayed in Tab. 2.5-8.

Tab. 2.5-8: Chemical composition of the ZA4Aa formation water after the experiments (VSB laboratories).

Partial Sample	pH	ρ at 15 °C (g/cm ³)	conductivity (mS/cm)	SO ₄ ⁻² (mg/l)	Cl ⁻ (mg/l)	HCO ₃ ⁻ (mg/l)	NH ⁺ (mg/l)	K ⁺ (mg/l)
After 1 month	6.7	1.016	36.9	640	13250.56	2702.3	9.1	257
After 3 months	6.9	1.016	35.3	660	12727.63	3440.4	15.8	256
After 3A months	7.3	1.017	34.8	630	13294.88	3050	17.5	295
After 4 months	7.2	1.016	37.2	550	13046.7	3225.7	19.4	463
After 6 months	6.8	1.018	38	540	12444	3660	19.1	334

Partial Sample	Mg ²⁺ (mg/l)	Na ⁺ (g/l)	Ca ²⁺ (mg/l)	Li ⁺ (mg/l)	Sr ²⁺ (mg/l)	Mn (mg/l)	Fe (mg/l)	TOC (mg/l)
After 1 month	107	4.57	285	2.75	17.0	0.882	<0.01	480
After 3 months	100	6.26	315	2.88	13.6	1.080	94.9	469
After 3A months	99.3	5.53	416	2.87	14.6	1.260	130.0	430
After 4 months	94.8	8.75	348	2.78	16.3	0.731	45187	450
After 6 months	92.7	6.77	702	2.72	13.4	0.421	60.8	484

Task 5.5 – Evaluation of changes in reservoir properties during and after CO₂ injection

Changes in composition of the original brine after interaction with rock and CO₂ saturation are summarized in Tab. 2.5-9.

Tab. 2.5-9: Changes in chemical composition of the brine after the experiments running 1-6 months.

parameter	pH	ρ at 15 °C	conductivity	SO ₄ -2	Cl-	HCO ₃ -	NH ₄ +	K	Mg	Na	Ca	Li	Sr	Mn	Fe
units	[-]	[g/cm ³]	[mS/cm]	[mg/l]											
MND analysis	7.0715	1,017	36,5	535	12300	2580	32,6	252	107,0	8570	111	3,17	19,2	0,01	0,35
1st month analysis	6.716	1,016	36,9	640	13251	2702	9,1	257	99,6	4570	285	2,75	17	0,88	0,01
3rd months analysis	6.896	1,016	35,3	660	12728	3440	15,8	256	99,3	6260	315	2,88	13,6	1,08	95
4th months analysis	7.220	1,016	37,2	550	13047	3226	19,4	463	94,8	8750	348	2,78	16,3	0,731	18,9
6th months analysis	6.813	1,018	38,0	540	12444	3660	19,1	334	92,7	6770	702	2,72	13,4	0,421	60,8

legend:

 decrease values
 increase values
 fluctuating values
 X stagnant values

Increased values of calcium and bicarbonate ions in brine during the experiments in reaction chamber indicate partial dissolution of carbonate minerals and transformation of the original reservoir rock. Decrease or fluctuating values of sodium, magnesium, strontium, potassium, manganese, iron, and lithium provides evidence of precipitation of secondary phases.

The rock samples used for experiments were subjected to XRD analysis at the specialized laboratory of the Department of Geological Engineering at VSB. XRD analysis of rock samples after each step of the experiments in reaction chamber shows:

- precipitation of calcite and dissolution of primary dolomite during the first month;
- formation of other secondary phases – kaolinite, muscovite, feldspar (albite, microcline and orthoclase);
- formation of iron-dolomite and chlorite at the end of the experiments.

The formation of secondary phases reduces the porosity of the primary rock and thus its permeability. This contributes to the stability of the rock environment. These results will be supplemented by geochemical models to be performed in 2023.

The second set of experiments in the reaction chambers included caprock samples and started at the end of 2022 (see Tab. 2.5-10). The solid samples were selected from the impermeable Carboniferous sandy-shaly siltstone interval of the Myslejovice Fm. (side seal of the reservoir) and from Paleogene silty rocks of the Nesvačilka Fm., Žarošice Mb. overlying the reservoir (primary caprock). The same brine was used as in case of the reservoir samples. Pressure and temperature conditions for the processes were set at 15 MPa and 53°C.

Tab. 2.5-10: Caprock samples used for second set of CO₂-fluid-rock experiments in VSB laboratory.

No	Well name # core_box_cm1_cm2	Sample Measured depth (m)	Sample TVDSS (m)	Chrono- stratigraphy	Lithostratigraphy Formation	Type of rock
1	ZA3_1_3_95_97	1462.95	1240.09	Mid. Paleogene	Žarošice Mb.	Seal
2	ZA4_1_5_51_72	1866.51	1573.41	Mid. Paleogene	Žarošice Mb.	Seal
3	ZA3_6_2_70_75	1884.70	1661.20	Lower Carboniferous	Myslejovice Fm.	Seal

The experiments with caprocks are still running and will be finalised in 2023.

Deviations and changes

Mid-term evaluation of the results (Milestone M5.1) took place in September 2022: The analytical works are slightly delayed because of delay in providing additional core samples (mainly from caprock) by MND, which was a consequence of the damages of the core repository at Lužice caused by the tornado. Additional caprock samples were provided only in May 2022 and cuttings in December 2022. Optimization of the works to be done in the second phase of WP5 includes prioritizing of the necessary complementary analyses of the cuttings and bringing the experiments with caprocks to a successful end in mid-2023. In general, the WP5 has still good chances to be completed according to the plan, including achievement of all planned results.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

No results were planned for this reporting period.

Milestones

Milestone	Date	Description
M5.1	achieved 09/2022	Mid-term evaluation of the results and optimization of the works to be done in the second phase of WP5

2.6 WORK PACKAGE 6 – Risk analysis

Summary

The main objective of the work package is to assess leakage risks related to CO₂ storage in the Zar-3 hydrocarbon field and to compile the findings in a risk assessment report. In 2022 the work was performed according to the plan; the main focus was on compiling and analysing data for the purpose of hazard characterization. Two workshops were held during the year: a physical meeting in Bergen in May, and a virtual meeting on WebEx in December. The work was performed by NORCE (WP leader), CGS and MND.

Task 6.1 – Hazard characterisation

Large parts of required data were gathered in 2021, however some further data was also collected in 2022. This included coordinates for abandoned wellbore locations and area of interest, well design schematics, historical meteorological conditions (wind speed, wind direction, cloud proportion) for the area of interest, caprock thickness maps (see Fig. 2.6-1). Furthermore, relevant information from results R1.2 (pedology, geology, conflicts of interest, etc.) and R4.3 (impact of cooling and re-pressurization of the field stresses in context with rock strength) have been handed over to WP6.

Fig. 2.6-1: Examples of collected data relevant to WP6, here showing from left well schematic, wellbore locations, wind speed histogram for area of interest, caprock thickness map for Paleogene and wind direction radar chart based on historical data from area of interest.

Task 6.1 is structured in four main sub-tasks, each addressing a particular leakage scenario. These are (i) leakage from abandoned wellbores, (ii) leakage through the caprock, (iii) leakage along faults and (iv) leakage by exceeding spill point, of which scenario (i) has by far been the main priority thus far.

To analyse the magnitude of leakage rates for scenario (i), it was decided to use a modified (for CO₂) version of NORCE’s P&A Leakage Calculator, a well-specific, stochastically

based framework for quantitatively assessing leakage rates from abandoned wellbores. The framework is outlined in Fig. 2.6-2.

Fig. 2.6-2: Stochastic framework for quantitative assessment of leakage rates from abandoned wellbores.

Required data was collected for all wells in of the area of interest. Geological data and well designs were provided by CGS and MND, respectively. Assumptions on prevailing reservoir pressure were established together with WP3 and WP4 teams. Likely leakage pathways for gas to migrate out of the wellbore were identified for each well, based on locations of reservoir, plugs, casing cement and other well barriers. As the existing state of any well barrier was not directly obtainable, and cement bond logs (CBL) were not available, assumptions were made stochastically of the degree of failed state of the well barriers. Under these assumptions, it was possible to generate preliminary leakage rate distributions for all wells of interest. The methodological approach and leakage rate distributions for CO₂ for all wells are shown in Figures 2.6-3 and 2.6-4.

Fig. 2.6-3: Example of assessment of leakage rate for a particular abandoned wellbore. The surrounding formation, the well design and the well barriers are basic input parameters. A likely leakage path (breaches in cemented well barriers), as well as the range and distribution of microannuli apertures in cement/casing or cement/formation interfaces are established to describe the state of the well barriers. The resulting simulations provide a distribution of leakage rate over time.

Fig. 2.6-4: Preliminary leakage simulations of CO₂ from all abandoned wellbores in the area of interest, showing for each wellbore 10th percentile, mean and 90th percentile CO₂ leakage rate (m³/s).

For scenarios (ii), (iii) and (iv), evaluations are strongly dependent on the geological modelling and understanding of the underground storage structure. For caprock integrity, a separate workshop has been held with WP4, and a handover document has been provided, that outlines an evaluation of failure conditions for both various stress changes

due to repressurization and cooling. Faults and spill point evaluations are now ongoing with respect to outlining important factors, and will be finalized once dynamic simulations in WP3 provide appropriate input to WP6.

Task 6.2 – Exposure assessment

Using preliminary leakage rates simulation results from Task 6.1, work in Task 6.2 has been focused on establishing a model to quantify possible concentration levels of gas at various distance from a release point, using, in addition to leakage rates, local meteorological data and a Gaussian plume model. Using this approach, various release scenarios have been generated, as shown in Figure 2.6-5, where CO₂ concentration levels are shown at increasing distance from wellhead, for wells ZA1, ZA3 and ZA7.

Fig. 2.6-5: Utilization of simulated leakage rates for various abandoned wellbores combined with local meteorological data and a Gaussian plume model, to produce preliminary gas concentration levels at various distances from release point.

Task 6.3 – Effects assessment

The effects assessment work has been focused on establishing a model that maps possible gas release scenarios in the impacted area, and assessing what could be impacted for given areas, with focus on human safety and the environment. Preliminary impact scenarios at geographic locations of abandoned wellbores have been generated. CGS has provided various maps of the area of interest and its uses that will be used in the last stage of the work when risks for various receptors (humans, animals, infrastructure, etc.) will be quantified.

Fig. 2.6-6: Preliminary simulated concentration levels of leaked CO₂, distributed geographically, for wells ZA1, ZA3 and ZA7.

Task 6.4 – Risk characterisation

This Task will start in January 2023.

Deviations and changes

No major deviations were encountered during the reporting period. The delay in handover of input information for risk identification from 2021 has been made up and the relevant Milestone M6.1 was achieved in March 2022.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

No results were planned for this reporting period.

Milestones

Milestone	Date	Description
M6.1	achieved 03/2022	Handover of required information (maps, P&A schematics, logs, geological formations, etc.) for risk identification

2.7 WORK PACKAGE 7 – Monitoring

Summary

The main objective of this WP is to prepare a storage site monitoring plan in the sense of Section 9 of the Act No. 85/2012 Sb. on the Storage of Carbon Dioxide in Natural Underground Geological Formations. The main effort in 2022 was focused on the baseline atmogeochemical monitoring, monitoring of natural and induced seismicity, monitoring of shallow groundwater and preparation works for the reservoir containment monitoring. The work was generally performed according to the plan with minor deviations. All Project Partners were involved under the leadership of CGS as WP leader. The planned result R7.8 “Feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods for CO₂ plume monitoring” was postponed to 2023 to allow for utilisation of additional input data and, thus, achieving higher quality. Monitoring data were collected and processed throughout the year with the prospect of integration in the WP7 results planned for 2023.

Task 7.1 – Methods and data

The planned feasibility study (sub-contract) to assess the applicability of seismic survey – the most powerful monitoring tool for mapping the extension of the CO₂ plume in the subsurface – at Zar-3 (result R7.8) was postponed to 2023 to allow for utilisation of the new 3D geological model of the storage complex as input (see chapter ‘Deviations and changes’ below for details).

Task 7.2 – Atmogeochemical monitoring

Atmogeochemical monitoring belongs to the group of basic monitoring methods used for all terrestrial CO₂ storage sites. The main aim is to determine the areal distribution of important soil gas components (CO₂, CH₄, O₂ and TP – total petroleum), and identify and monitor anomalies (if any), based on (1) periodical and (2) continuous soil gas monitoring.

For the periodical monitoring, a grid of 95 monitoring points was defined at the beginning of the project and was also used in 2022 (Fig. 2.7-1). At each point, the soil gas composition was measured by CGS, using the Ecoprobe-5 portable instrument from 80 – 100 cm deep drilled holes. In 2022, 3 periodical monitoring campaigns were performed – in winter (February), spring (May) and summer-autumn (September). Since the majority of the area is cultivated fields, it was not possible to prepare more monitoring campaigns in the spring-autumn period due to the field crops and harvest campaigns.

Fig. 2.7-1: Area map with the grid of 95 monitoring points (black dots) used for the periodical monitoring and positions of five IGS permanent atmogeochemical probes (orange dots) used for continuous monitoring. Left: detailed view of the Zar-3 field (yellow polygon) and protected deposit area (cyan polygon) with production licence areas (green rectangles); right: overview of the area of interest (red rectangle).

For the purposes of field data interpretation, weather conditions, in particular temperature, atmospheric pressure and rainfalls total have been collected and stored. During all campaigns of 2022, 20 calibration soil gas samples were collected for laboratory chromatographic analysis. Atmogeochemical contour maps of the site area showing content of selected components in soil gas (CO₂, CH₄, O₂ and TP – total petroleum) and its changes with time are the main outcome of this work. An example is provided in Fig. 2.7-2 where the distribution of CO₂ in soil gas during the 2022 monitoring campaigns is shown. The monitoring campaigns are carried out in the same period (season) of individual years for the correlation purposes.

Fig. 2.7-2: CO₂ distribution in soil gas during the 2022 monitoring campaigns.

The continuous monitoring is performed by five IGS permanent atmogeochemical probes. Their location is shown in Fig. 2.7-1. The probes monitor CO₂ content in soil gas since June 2021 (Fig. 2.7-3). The main aim is to collect continuous data on CO₂ content in soil gas over several years for a more detailed evaluation of seasonal changes and potential influence of weather conditions (e.g. rainfalls total, atmospheric pressure etc.).

Significantly higher values of CO₂ content in soil gas could be observed during summer seasons of both 2021 and 2022 (Fig. 2.7-3), which is related to the increased vegetation activity. In 2022, the permanent IGS probes were in operation for the whole year, with the exception of short periods needed for probes calibration (April) and batteries replacement (both in April and October, Fig. 2.7-3). Comparison of both the periodical and continuous monitoring represents a powerful tool to define the atmogeochemical baseline for the Task 7.6 Site monitoring plan.

Fig. 2.7-3: Variations of CO₂ content in soil gas measured by five IGS permanent monitoring stations labelled in different colour (for stations position see Fig. 2.7-1). The black trend line represents weekly moving average of all stations.

Task 7.3 – Seismic monitoring

Seismic monitoring is another representative of basic monitoring methods used for all CO₂ storage sites onshore. In 2022, the GFU team continued the operation of the permanent site seismic network consisting of 5 monitoring stations (Fig. 2.7-4), which are in operation since August/September 2021. As the stations record data in off-line mode, the measured data need to be repeatedly downloaded. Consequently, the preliminary data processing (i.e. format conversion and activations) was performed. A two-step procedure of seismograms interpretation was used: (1) by preliminary automatic picking and (2) by manual detailed interpretation of relevant seismograms. The newly created bulletin is supplemented by data from the bulletin of the Czech National seismological network. The relevant events are being re-localized to obtain their more precise location.

Fig. 2.7-4: Map with positions of the permanent and temporal seismic monitoring networks in the Zar-3 area.

Both monitoring and data processing ran continuously during 2022 without any principal issues. The final 2022 seismic bulletin version based on the Zar-3 monitoring network measurements is expected to be finalized at the end of March 2023. The seismic events observed in the wider region are shown in Fig. 2.7-5.

Fig. 2.7-5: Events observed in the region close to Zar-3 area – preliminary partial results. Some of the newly detected events are located near the Dobrá Voda site in Slovakia and near the Austrian-Slovakian border.

In addition to the planned activity, a temporal seismic network of 6 seismic stations was installed and put in operation in May/June 2022. This network was planned to enlarge the network detection ability during the planned Injection Step-Rate Test (see WP3 for details). The aim was to add temporal stations to monitor induced seismicity during the test itself and to detect events related to potential cracks opening, spreading etc., which cannot be generally retrieved from the 5 permanent network stations records. Unfortunately, the Step-Rate Test was cancelled for technical reasons just a few days before its planned start and the effort related to deployment of additional seismic stations has gone to waste.

A change in the T7.3 scope and methodology compared to the original proposal of the project has been proposed and approved by the project Management Board in 2022. It was decided to significantly prolong the operation period of the permanent seismic network. Originally, the seismic monitoring was supposed to be closed in the second half of 2022. The savings in the GFU budget (mainly due to the reduced travel costs during the COVID period and cheaper seismic stations operation), enabled GFU to modify the budget and shift some saved costs to 2023. By this, a prolonged operation of the seismic network up to 2023 and corresponding data processing costs can be covered. This is an important extension to the originally planned seismic monitoring in Zar-3 area. Extension of the monitoring period has been endorsed by all Project Partners, supporting the argument that prolonged operation of the seismic network will provide useful additional information to WP7 and the project as a whole.

Task 7.4 – Shallow groundwater monitoring

The shallow groundwater monitoring is essential for both understanding the shallow groundwater regime on the site, and establishing a baseline for subsequent monitoring of groundwater quality in later stages of site development. This Task is executed by CGS and VSB.

To cover all seasons of the 2022, the shallow hydrogeological monitoring campaigns were performed by CGS in March, June, October and December. The groundwater level (m), spring yield (l/s), electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), pH (-) and water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) have been monitored. In 2022, 16 monitoring points/objects (out of 19 that were measured in 2021, Fig. 2.7-6) have been monitored. Those are e.g. shallow wells, boreholes and springs. Access to 3 original monitoring points was not possible in 2022 due to various reasons, such as new fence construction or the frozen borehole lid in winter.

Fig. 2.7-6: Position of 19 original groundwater monitoring points near the Zar-3 site. Access to 3 monitoring points (labelled in red) was not possible in 2022.

Groundwater level measurements were performed in five boreholes and five wells. Measurements were made with the water-level indicator cable with ca. 1 cm accuracy (Fig. 2.7-7).

Fig. 2.7-7: Results of groundwater level measurements (m) in monitored objects on the site in 2021-2022.

Spring yield was monitored in two cases. The water flowing out of the spring was collected in a container – the time taken to fill the container was measured and the yield in litres per second determined (Fig. 2.7-8).

Fig. 2.7-8: Spring yields (litres /sec) of monitored objects ZA008 and ZA019 measured in 2021-2022.

The conductivity of a groundwater is highly dependent on the concentration of dissolved salts and other chemical species that ionize in the solution. Electrical conductivity of water samples is used as an indicator of how salt-free, ion-free, or impurity-free the sample is; the purer the water, the lower the conductivity and vice versa. Conductivity measurements in water are usually reported as specific conductance, relative to the conductivity of pure water at 25 °C. An EC meter capable of providing such values was used to measure water conductivity at Zar-3 (Fig. 2.7-9).

The pH indicates the concentration of hydrogen ions in the solution. At 25 °C, solutions with a pH less than 7 are acidic, and solutions with a pH above 7 are basic. Solutions with a pH of 7 at this temperature are neutral (e.g. pure water). The measurement results are shown in Fig. 2.7-10.

Fig. 2.7-9: Results of water electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) measurements in monitored objects on the site in 2021-2022.

Fig. 2.7-10: Measured water pH (-) in monitored objects on the site in 2021-2022.

The water temperature reflects the depth of its circulation; water with a shallow circulation is more reflective to changes in air temperature throughout the year and vice versa. The measurement results are shown in (Fig. 2.7-11).

Fig. 2.7-11: Water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) in monitored objects on the site in 2021-2022.

The measured water temperatures reflect the effect of seasonal variations in air temperature and the depth of water circulation. Waters with deeper circulation have less difference between the temperature values measured in the warmer and colder parts of the year than waters with circulation closer to the surface.

The preliminary results of shallow groundwater monitoring show that the data obtained in 2021 and 2022 correspond to the expected natural conditions characteristic of the site of interest. The monitoring will continue in 2023 as planned, no changes are required.

Dipole electromagnetic profiling (DEMP)

In 2022, VSB processed the data of the dipole electromagnetic profiling (DEMP) geophysical survey conducted in 2021. More than 4 400 values measured along 17 profiles with a variable length of 600 – 1 700 m were processed and the map of apparent conductivity (Fig 7.2-12) was created. The area measured by the DEMP method covers over 1.2 km² (rectangle ca. 900 × 1 500 m). The results will contribute to the construction of the shallow hydrogeological model of the site, to better identification or prediction of possible preferential leakage pathways, and to designing effective infrastructure for monitoring of possible CO₂ leakage in Task 7.6 Site monitoring plan. In spite of strong negative correlation between conductivity and altitude, the areas of conductive domains need to be further analysed from the point of view of occurrence of potential preferential pathways for CO₂ flux.

Fig. 2.7-12: Results of ground-based dipole electromagnetic profiling performed at the Zar-3 site. The survey showed three main zones characterized as relatively isometric low-conductivity anomalies (<45 mS.m-1) with 300–400 m in diameter.

Hydrogeological model of groundwater flow

In order to assess potential contamination of shallow groundwater by possible CO₂ leakage, work on a regionally conceived shallow hydrogeological model of the overburden of the storage area has been initiated by VSB in the second half of 2022 by collecting of the input data. The work will continue in 2023.

Task 7.5 – Reservoir containment monitoring

The main purpose of this Task is to prepare a reservoir containment monitoring system. The task is executed by NORCE and MND, under NORCE leadership. The advanced monitoring technology developed at NORCE (Shchipanov et al., 2019⁸) will be evaluated in this task combining results of reservoir simulations with time-lapse pressure transient analysis. During the reporting period, the main attention was paid to finishing the extended analysis of dynamic data (from Task 3.2), where additional focus was on boundary conditions of the reservoir and their reflection in real pressure transient data, available for the field (see the T3.2 report chapter above). Analysis of the boundary conditions and their reflections in the transients helps in getting reservoir base-line response to be used in further evaluations of deviations from the response due to potential leakage, e.g. via legacy wells in this task. The reservoir simulation activities planned in 2022 in this task were moved to 2023 due to the delay with history matching the reservoir model in WP3. This will lead to delay with delivering the result R7.6 ‘Data set and report with results of reservoir containment monitoring’ planned for March 2023. Approximately 3-4 months will be needed to deliver R7.6 after the history matched reservoir model is available for T7.5.

Task 7.6 – Site monitoring plan

This task will start in January 2023, however, the results from other relevant Work Packages and other WP7 Tasks are being gradually collected, together with experience from other CO₂ storage projects worldwide.

Deviations and changes

Some deviations from the work plan were reported in WP7, however, none of them will have negative influence on achievement of WP objectives or execution of other Work Packages. Delays are reported in T7.1 and T7.5:

Task 7.1: The planned feasibility study (sub-contract) on the applicability of seismic survey for monitoring of the CO₂ plume at Zar-3 (result R7.8), originally scheduled for 2022, was postponed to 2023. The reason is that it has been deemed useful to wait for the new 3D geological model of the storage complex that was prepared in WP2 and finalised in summer 2022 only. This model represents an additional valuable component of input in the feasibility study. The postponement was discussed and approved by the CO₂-SPICER Management Board. The corresponding public tender procedure was organised in autumn 2022, and the sub-contract will be realised in 2023 (see WP10, Task 10.2

⁸ Shchipanov A.A., Kollbotn L., Berenblyum R. Characterization and monitoring of reservoir flow barriers from pressure transient analysis for CO₂ injection in saline aquifers. International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control. Volume 91, December 2019, doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2019.102842.

description for details on the public tender). The final delivery date of the study – end of October 2023 – still allows for using the study results in Task 7.6 for preparation of the Site monitoring plan (result V5; deadline 02/2024).

Task 7.5: The work is behind schedule due to the delay with history matching of the reservoir model (WP3) that represents an important input in T7.5. The delay will be compensated in 2023, so that the planned input to the Site monitoring plan (T7.6) is provided in due time.

A change in the work plan has been agreed in Task 7.3 (Seismic monitoring) where the monitoring period has been extended (see T7.3 description for details).

WP results achieved in the reporting period

Other results		
No.	Result title	Date of submission
R7.8	Feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods for CO2 plume monitoring	Planned 12/2022 Postponed to 10/2023

Milestones

No milestones are defined for this Work Package.

2.8 WORK PACKAGE 8 – Scenarios of future development

Summary

The main objective of the Work Package is to prepare future site development plans, and design surface and subsurface facilities for the selected pilot site. The work has started as planned in the previous reporting period and was carried out since then according to the work plan. NORCE coordinated the work as WP leader; CGS and MND provided contributions to Tasks 8.1 and 8.3. The activities in Task 8.2 were carried out by NORCE and MND.

Task 8.1 – Value chain analysis for CO₂ supply, transport, EOR and storage

The work continued on identifying the most promising capture and storage sites in the region to feed the scenarios development in Task 8.3. The work in Task 8.1 focused on both short- and long-term value chains. The first one represents scenarios for the CO₂ storage pilot and field-scale implementation, while the other one corresponds to development of a longer-term regional scenario.

CGS continued consultation with industrial companies that expressed interest in capturing and storing their CO₂ emissions in the region. The most promising cooperation (that could have led to development of a feasible field-scale implementation scenario) was developed with a Czech energy company interested in construction of a blue hydrogen facility near the Zar-3 field. This project was developed up to the stage of a pre-feasibility study and basic technical specifications of the planned hydrogen production facility, including the integrated CO₂ capture plant, were provided to CO₂-SPICER. Unfortunately, the gas crisis in Europe that caused extreme increase in prices of natural gas – the basic feedstock of blue hydrogen production, and the shortage of natural gas supplies to Europe connected with the Russian attack on Ukraine led to the suspension of the project. Nevertheless, the scenario still has a development potential for future, especially if domestic natural gas can be used as feedstock, and will be further considered in the project.

Consultations were also held with representatives of a glass factory located ca. 12 km from the Zar-3 site that uses natural gas for heat production and emits ca. 75 kt CO₂ annually. This would also represent an interesting source-sink match for a field-scale implementation scenario. Regrettably, the gas crisis affected this CO₂ emitter as well, and due to a critical economic situation of the company this scenario has become non-realistic.

In view of the above-mentioned facts, the WP8 team started a re-evaluation of the CO₂ emission sources in the area with the objective to identify additional relevant source-sink scenarios, including assessment of possible combination of the Zar-3 storage site with a Direct Air Capture project (aiming at a carbon dioxide removal /CDR/ scenario) or possible integration of the site into a regional storage hub.

As far as the regional scenario is concerned, CGS and MND started preparing an overview of CO₂ storage potential and mapped CO₂ storage sites in the broader area of interest that will be based on earlier work by CGS and recent storage site development efforts by MND. CGS prepared an updated map of saline aquifers with CO₂ storage potential in the area (see Fig. 2.8-1), supplemented with basic characteristics of the identified structures, that will now be completed by additional data provided by MND.

Fig. 2.8-1 Indicative map of saline aquifers with CO₂ storage potential in broader area of interest (updated by CGS from earlier projects).

NORCE has proceeded to build a network model of the region using the planning tool developed in the Strategy CCUS project⁹.

Task 8.2 – Design of facilities for pilot implementation

This task has started as planned and is tightly coordinated with pilot simulation activities carried out in WP3. Two transport and intermittent storage scenarios are being currently drafted. Both are based on an approx. 120 ton/day injection scenario currently planned in WP3. The EU pilot limit (100 000 tons) would then be reached in under 3 years of injection. The scenario assumes truck transport, see Fig 2.8-2.

⁹ Nermoen, A., Berenblyum, R., Coussy, P., Guichet, X., Canteli, P., Mesquita, P., Carneiro, J., Khrulenko, A., Rocha, P.A., Martínez, R. A Techno-Economic Analysis Tool for Regional CO₂ Capture, Transport, Use and Storage Scenarios (July 8, 2022). Proceedings of the 16th Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies Conference (GHGT-16) 23-24 Oct 2022, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4271525> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4271525>

Fig. 2.8-2: Potential truck route to site

Scenario 1 assumes cryogenic transport of CO₂, using 14-ton trucks (requiring 9 trucks per day). However, as it is a low pressure and temperature option (-30°C and 20 bar), it would require additional pumping and heating capacity to avoid hydrate and icing issues in the wells and in the reservoir.

Scenario 2 is a high pressure system (200 bar, ambient temperature). The disadvantage here is that each truck can carry only 8 tons, bringing the total number of trucks per day to 15.

Setup showing both scenarios is shown in Figure 2.8-3.

Fig. 2.8-3: Scheme showing both low and high pressure gathering systems.

An analysis and choice of the transport system will be carried in the next reporting period.

Task 8.3 – Scenarios for future site development

During the second reporting period several potential scenarios have been designed and the further plan of work has been put together.

The work will start with high-level estimation of five different injection scenarios. Based on the evaluation of the scenarios, the base case and the best alternative will be selected for verification using the reservoir model from WP3. The scenarios for rough TEA / LCA (techno-economic and life-cycle analysis) are:

- Base case: storage after gas blowdown (i.e. complete production of the remaining gas in the reservoir)
- Alternative 1: Blowdown supported by CO₂ injection into water zone.
- Alternative 2: Blue hydrogen from Zar-3 gas
- Alternative 3 Classical EOR (Enhanced Oil Recovery)
- Alternative 4: Direct air capture.

Main Key Performance Indicators for the scenarios are: amount of abated CO₂, cost per ton abated.

Deviations and changes

The transfer of the history-matched model from WP3 is delayed (see WP3 chapter for details) and the corresponding Milestone M8.1 has not been achieved. Its achievement is expected in early 2023. This deviation will not affect the overall outcomes of WP3 as the use of the simulation model was originally planned in the late phase of the project.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

No results were planned for this reporting period.

Milestones

Milestone	Date	Description
M8.1	Not achieved, (planned 08/2022)	Transfer of history matched model from WP3

2.9 WORK PACKAGE 9 – Communication and dissemination

Summary

The main aim of project communication and dissemination activities is to create awareness of the existence of the project, disseminate project results to identified target groups to achieve the planned impact, raise general awareness of CCS as an important climate change mitigation technology and highlight the bilateral Czech-Norwegian cooperation based on project funding from Norway Grants.

The work in WP9 was carried out according to the work plan. It was governed by the Communication Plan that has been updated in October 2022 (result R9.5). The updated Plan summarises the achievements of project dissemination and communication activities from the beginning of the projects and reflects the recent changes on the national and international CCS scene in the slightly updated plan of activities for the remaining part of project duration. The updated Communication Plan is submitted together with other project results as an attachment to the Interim Report.

CGS led the WP9 activities as WP leader, all Project Partners contributed to the work.

Task 9.1 – Project events

No project events were planned for 2022.

Task 9.2 – Website

The project website at the address “<https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz>” that was created in both Czech and English versions at the beginning of the project has been continuously updated during the whole year 2022 by adding fresh project news, promotion material, presentations from conferences and links to publications. An update of the graphic style of the web has been made to comply with the new graphic style of the project (see Task 9.3). A webpage screenshot from the updated website is shown in Fig. 2.9-1.

The website also offers a link to the information portal on CCS technology that has been operated by CGS since 2006 at <http://www.geology.cz/ccs>. Regular updates of this portal were also part of CO₂-SPICER communication activities in 2022.

CO₂ Storage Pilot in a Carbonate Reservoir

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Press Releases

- CO₂-SPICER - press release

Promotional materials

- CO₂-SPICER - Project information leaflet

Presentations

- **Basin modeling of a pilot CO₂ storage in a dolomite reservoir, Bohemian Massif, Czech Republic**
 Presentation of the CO₂-SPICER project results at the Petroleum Systems Technology Days 2022; Aachen, (August 2022).
 Authors: J. Franců, R. Prochác, P. Jirman, L. Jurenka, J. Vácha, V. Hladík (CGS), V. Opletal (MND), W. Wheeler (NORCE).
- **Comparison of two candidate hydrocarbon fields for a CO₂ storage pilot in the Czech Republic**
 Presentation of results of CO₂-SPICER, REPP-CO₂ and ENOS projects at the 2nd EAGE Geoscience and Engineering for the Energy Transition Conference (GET2021); online (November 2021). Authors: V. Hladík, R. Prochác, M. Pereszlényi (CGS), R. Berenblyum, A. Shchipanov, A. Nermoen, E.P. Ford (NORCE).
- **History of Czech-Norwegian cooperations on CCS**
 Presentation at the Norwegian-Czech CCS webinar organised by the Norwegian Embassy in Prague; online (September 2021). Author: V. Hladík (CGS).
- **CO₂-SPICER: CO₂ Storage Pilot in a Carbonate Reservoir**
 Presentation of the CO₂-SPICER project at the Norwegian-Czech CCS webinar organised by the Norwegian Embassy in Prague; online (September 2021). Author: R. Berenblyum (NORCE).
- **CO₂-SPICER: Czech-Norwegian project to prepare a CO₂ storage pilot in a carbonate reservoir**
 Presentation of the CO₂-SPICER project at the 11th Trondheim CCS conference (TCCS-11); online (June 2021). Authors: V. Hladík, R. Prochác, P. Jirman (CGS), V. Opletal, M. Pagáč (MND), R. Berenblyum, A. Shchipanov, E. Ford, A. Nermoen (NORCE).
- **Diagenesis and dolomitization of Jurassic carbonate rocks in the SE Bohemian Massif**
 Presentation of research results related to Jurassic carbonates, including CO₂-SPICER project, WPS, at the 35th IAS Meeting of Sedimentology; online (June 2021).
- **CO₂ storage conditions in Czechia**
 Presentation at the Conference on CO₂ capture, storage and use for Czech industrial companies organised by the BeePartner company within the CCUS CZ-NO project; online (April 2021). Author: V. Hladík (CGS).
- **CO₂-SPICER: CO₂ storage pilot in a carbonate reservoir**
 Presentation of the CO₂-SPICER project at the Czech-Norwegian conference on CO₂ capture and storage – the Launch event of CO₂-SPICER a METAMORPH projects; online (March 2021). Authors: V. Hladík (CGS), V. Opletal (MND), R. Berenblyum (NORCE).
- **Assessment of trans-boundary effects at LBr-1 CO₂ storage pilot site and regulatory solutions**
 Presentation of results of REPP-CO₂, ENOS and CO₂-SPICER project at the GHGT-15 international conference; online (March 2021). Autoři: V. Hladík, J. Franců, V. Kolejka, M. Pereszlényi (CGS), L. Kollbotn, E. Ford (NORCE), M. Jankulár (ŠGÚDŠ), M. Koenen (TNO).
- **Presentations from the conference 'Czech-Norwegian Cooperation on CCS'**
 Set of ten presentations from the online launch event of CO₂-SPICER and METAMORPH projects funded from the TACR KAPPA programme; 5 March 2021

Publications

- **Assessment of a mature hydrocarbon field in SE Czech Republic for a CO₂ storage pilot**
 An article of the CO₂-SPICER project results at the 16th International Conference on Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies. GHGT-16, Lyon, France (23rd -27th October 2022).
 Authors: Vít Hladík, Vladimír Opletal, Roman Berenblyum, Michal Matloch Porzer, Róbert Prochác, Petr Jirman, Anton Shchipanov, Anders Nermoen, Eric P. Ford.
- Franců, J., Prochác, R., Jirman, P., Jurenka, L., Vácha, J., Hladík, V., Opletal, V., Wheeler, W. (2022): Basin modeling of a pilot CO₂- storage in a dolomite reservoir Bohemian Massif, Czech Republic. Book of abstracts, Petroleum Systems technology Days 2022, Aachen, 30 Aug – 1 sep 2022, p. 25.
- Franců, J., Jurenka, L., Jirman, P. (2021) Diagenesis and dolomitization of Jurassic carbonate rocks in the SE Bohemian Massif. Book of Abstracts, 35th IAS Meeting of Sedimentology, Prague, 21-25 June 2021; p. 168.
- Hladík, V., Prochác, R., Opletal, V., Pagáč, M., Jirman, P., Berenblyum, R., Shchipanov, A., Ford, E. P., Nermoen, A. (2021): CO₂-SPICER – Czech-Norwegian project to prepare a CO₂ storage pilot in a carbonate reservoir. Short Papers from the 11th International Trondheim CCS Conference, 21-23 June 2021; pp. 318-322.
- Hladík, V., Kollbotn, L., Franců, J., Kolejka, V., Pereszlényi, M., Jankulár, M., Ford, E.P., Koenen, M. (2021): Assessment of Trans-Boundary Effects at LBr-1 CO₂ Storage Pilot Site and Regulatory Solutions. Proceedings of the 15th Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies Conference, 15-18 March 2021.; 17 pp.

Fig. 2.9-1: CO₂-SPICER project website (updated English version) – subpage Downloads with overview of project communication outcomes.

Task 9.3 – Presentations and publications

The update of the Communication and Design Manual of EEA and Norway Grants that was announced by TACR in February 2022 has brought, among other changes, a ban on using project logos. Due to the fact that CO2-SPICER project logo has become an integral part of project communication activities since the very beginning of the project, CO2-SPICER management team asked in March 2022 for an exemption from this ban and a permission to continue with use the project logo. This exemption has been approved by the Financial Mechanism Office in Brussels in October 2022, however, with the condition that the project logo must always be coupled with the logo of Norway Grants.

This condition meant, in practice, the necessity to modify not only the project logo itself, but also all presentation materials like the PowerPoint presentation template, Word document / project report template, poster template, project banner, background for online meetings and conferences, etc. The new graphic style had also to be applied to project website and for the preparation of all new communication outputs like posters, reports, leaflets, newsletters, etc. The new project graphic style (Figs. 2.9-2 and 2.9-3) was prepared in November 2022 and has been used since then.

Fig. 2.9-2: New project logotypes.

Fig. 2.9-3: New project PowerPoint presentation template.

In 2022, the project and its results were presented at four top international conferences; the following talks were given:

- **CO₂ storage pilot project in a depleting hydrocarbon field in Czechia**

Presentation of CO₂-SPICER project results at the 15th CO₂GeoNet Open Forum; Venice (September 2022). Authors: V. Hladík, R. Prochác (CGS), V. Opletal, M. Pagáč (MND) & the CO₂-SPICER project team.

- **CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir**

Presentation of the CO₂-SPICER project at the 55th Continental European Energy Council meeting; Praha (October 2022). Authors: V. Opletal, L. Klímová (MND), V. Hladík, J. Rez (CGS).

- **Assessment of a mature hydrocarbon field in SE Czech Republic for a CO₂ storage pilot**

Presentation of CO₂-SPICER project results at the 16th Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies conference (GHGT-16); Lyon (October 2022). Authors: V. Hladík, R. Prochác, P. Jirman (CGS), V. Opletal (MND), R. Berenblyum, A. Shchipanov, A. Nermoen, E. P. Ford (NORCE), M. Matloch Porzer (VSB) & the CO₂-SPICER project team (Fig. 2.9-3).

- **Basin modelling of a pilot CO₂ storage in a dolomite reservoir, Bohemian Massif, Czech Republic.**

Presentation of the CO₂-SPICER project results at the Petroleum Systems Technology Days 2022; Aachen. (August 2022). Authors: J. Franců, R. Prochác, P. Jirman, L. Jurenka, J. Vácha, V. Hladík (CGS), V. Opletal (MND), W. Wheeler (NORCE).

Fig. 2.9-4: Project coordinator Vit Hladik presenting CO₂-SPICER results at the GHGT-16 conference in Lyon.

In addition to the presentations, the related papers or paper abstracts were published in conference proceedings of these events. All project presentations and publications are available on project website at <https://co2-spicer.geology.cz/en/downloads>.

An important part of communication activities was the liaison with other projects funded by EEA/Norway Grants. Within the continued partnership with the CCS4CEE project (Building momentum for the long-term CCS deployment in the CEE region), funded from the Fund for Regional Cooperation of EEA/Norway Grants, CO₂-SPICER coordinator provided consultations and input to the National CCS roadmap for the Czech Republic that was prepared by EUROPEUM – the Czech partner of the CCS4CEE project. He also made a presentation on ‘Potential of the Czech Republic for geological storage of CO₂’ at the National CCS seminar that was organised by EUROPEUM on the occasion of launching the Czech CCS roadmap in Prague in June 2022.

Communication activities addressing industrial stakeholders included a series of bilateral consultations, both face-to-face and online, that were devoted to possibilities of utilisation of CCS technology as a solution for reduction of CO₂ emissions from industrial facilities, sharing information about the CO₂-SPICER project, discussions on future utilisation of its results and possible participation of the industry representatives in CO₂-SPICER End-User Group. The consulted companies included Českomoravský Cement a.s., ČD Cargo, SMOLO a.s. and Lafarge Cement Čížkovice. Consultations were also provided to the Ministry of Industry and Trade and the Ministry of Environmental of the Czech Republic. Within the liaison with the Ministry of Industry and Trade, project coordinator was invited to participate in the CCUS panel at the 16th SET Plan Conference that was organised in Prague in November 2022 as an important event of the Czech Presidency of the EU.

An important target group of project communication are university students. In 2021 Project Partner VSB attracted four students of the university (VSB – Technical University of Ostrava) to use topics solved within CO₂-SPICER as a basis for their final theses (see the 2021 Interim Report for details). Of these, one thesis has been successfully defended and two were still in progress in 2022 (one has been cancelled due to reasons on the student’s side):

- Master's thesis (defended):
Janani Augustin: Design of a Methodology for Laboratory Research of Filtration Parameters of the Rock-CO₂ System of the Žarošice Oil Field
- Bachelor thesis (in progress):
Josef Čožík: Utilization of Dipole Electromagnetic Profiling for CO₂ Monitoring Optimization at the Žarošice Site
- PhD thesis (in progress):
Adam Lacman: Research into the Influence of Carbon Dioxide on the Reservoir Properties of the Žarošice Oil Field

Another event targeting the students at VSB a Mineralogical get-together in the VSB campus in Ostrava where the CO₂-SPICER project was presented not only to students, but also to the general public.

In addition, a lecture on CCS was prepared by VSB for the students of the University of the Third Age (Fig. 2.9-5).

Fig. 2.9-5: Martin Klempa explaining principles of CO₂ geological storage to the students of the University of the Third Age at VSB.

The media interest attracted by CO₂-SPICER project implementation continued in 2022, even though with a lower intensity. Project Partners CGS and MND provided interested journalists with interviews and/or written information. Both thematically profiled media and those with nationwide coverage (e.g. iDNES.cz or INFO.cz) were interested in the project and the CCS technology in general. Examples of articles are shown in Fig. 2.9-6.

Fig. 2.9-6: Samples of articles in the media.

An overview of project media coverage is available on project website (Czech version) at <https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz/cs/zajimave-odkazy>.

Deviations and changes

The work in WP9 was carried out according to the work plan.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

Other results		
No.	Result title	Date of submission
R9.5	Updated Communication plan	10/2022

Milestones

No milestones are defined for this Work Package.

2.10 WORK PACKAGE 10 – Project management and reporting

Summary

The main goal of Work Package 10 is to ensure that the project runs as smoothly as possible. The project management structure as well as the duties at the different management levels were defined with a great attention to detail already during the project preparation stage, and have been enshrined in the Project Contract and the Partnership Agreement. Work Package 10 covers all project management, organisation and other related tasks; in 2022 the work progressed according to the plan. Work Package 10 was led by CGS (WP leader), with participation of all partners.

Task 10.1 – Project and Work Package Coordination and Management

This Task includes the management of the project and its key activities by the Project coordinator and leaders of the 10 defined Work Packages. In addition, it also covers the work of the project's three governing bodies – the General Assembly, Management Board and End-User Group.

The General Assembly is the highest decision-making body of the project. All partners involved in the project have one representative in the General Assembly, their respective voting powers (number of votes) corresponding to the scope of the partner's involvement in the project (in person-months of work). The second meeting of the General Assembly was held in the form of a personal meeting as a part of the project meeting in Brno on 7 December 2022 (unlike the previous online meeting during the pandemic situation). Minutes of the meeting are enclosed as a separate attachment to the Interim report, together with the Management Board meetings minutes.

The Management Board supports the Project coordinator in operative project management and housekeeping duties. It consists of the Project coordinator (Principal investigator) and the Work Packages leaders. In addition, the representatives of Project Partners also participate in Management Board meetings to ensure smooth flow of information across the whole project team. In 2022, Management Board meetings were held regularly once a month (usually on every second Thursday of each month) mainly in the form of teleconferences. The December Management Board meeting was organised as a physical meeting, as part of the project meeting in Brno. Minutes of the 12 meetings (in the order 15 to 26) are presented in a separate attachment to the Interim report.

The End-User Group has not been established yet, however, negotiations with potential Group participants (mostly industrial companies) continued in 2022 with promising results. The End-User Group is expected to be established in the 1st half of 2023.

Task 10.1 also covers the preparation and organisation of project meetings. During the 2nd project period, two project meetings were organized, both in-person, with the possibility of online connection for those participants who could not participate physically. The 3rd project meeting was held in Bergen (Norway) at NORCE headquarters on 24 May 2022 and the 4th meeting took place in Brno on 7 December 2022. Minutes of the meetings are provided in a separate attachment to the Interim report, together with the Management Board meetings minutes. In both cases, several WPs or topic-related joint workshops (modelling, future scenarios, geochemistry and geomechanics, risk assessment) were affiliated with the project meetings as needed.

Task 10.1 work is organised and implemented by CGS; the participation of other Project Partners corresponds to their involvement in the management of the different Work Packages. All partners were involved in the organized project meetings.

Task 10.2 – Project Administration, Liaison with Programme Operator, Reporting

The purpose of this Task is to provide administrative support to the project management team, both during routine, day-to-day operations and in the preparation of interim reports and the final report. The Task covers also the practicalities of ongoing cooperation with the Programme Operator (TACR) and the preparation of projects reports by the Project coordinator, WP leaders and Project Partners.

In January 2022, the 1st interim report for period 11/2020 – 12/2021 was submitted. For the successful submission of the report, we used the information and instructions from the special webinar „How to prepare interim report for 2021“ (in Czech only) organized by TACR on December 1, 2021. No further consultation from the project side was required even though TACR sent an offer for possible online consultation with KAPPA consultant.

A Project monitoring (on-site) audit organised by TACR took place in 2022 in two parts – the administrative and financial part was held on 20 June 2022 in Prague and was mainly devoted to check of costs incurred by project partners CGS and MND; the technical part of the audit took place separately online on 21 July 2022.

Within the financial part of the audit, minor shortcomings in the reporting of other direct costs (way of calculation of fuel costs of company cars used in the project) were detected at CGS and non-eligible costs in an amount of 1,340.82 CZK were identified. The relevant part of the grant (1,300.60 CZK) was returned to TACR based on an official request. Due to internal information flow issues at CGS the TACR documents were delivered to the project management team (based at the Brno Branch Office of CGS with delay), which caused both a delayed submission of the objection against the audit finding (which was then rejected due to the expiration of the term), and a delay in re-payment of the rejected sum. As a follow-up, based on a notice on suspicion of budgetary discipline breach sent by TACR, the Tax Office for the Capital of Prague started a tax audit at CGS in November 2022. The audit focused on the issue indicated in the TACR notice and was closed on 17 January 2023 with the result that no suspicion of budgetary discipline breach was found.

CGS has introduced corrective measures reacting to the TACR audit findings and subsequent slow reaction to it, which include in particular:

- Improvement of internal rules for communication between the CGS headquarters in Prague and the Brno branch office, as well to individual coordinators of research projects;
- Modification of the procedure for calculation of fuel costs of company cars used for travel in the project: The costs will be first calculated using the fuel costs stated in the invoices provided by the supplier (CCS Česká společnost pro platební karty s.r.o.) and then compared with the relevant Decree of the Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs that sets maximum fuel prices that can be used for project costs

according to the KAPPA programme rules. Based on this comparison, the lower of the two prices will be used for calculation of the costs.

Conclusions of the technical part of the TACR audit state that the project execution runs without problems and it is likely that the project will achieve its planned objectives. The registered delay of some results was not found to be critical. The complete audit report (in Czech only) is attached separately to the Interim report in the ISTA system.

The audit report also included recommendations on the process of approval of the N_{map} results, and the point was then also discussed and clarified with TACR at an online meeting (see below). The recommendation provided during the audit to use the internal review procedure of CGS (normally used for geological maps) could not be followed for the first N_{map} result in the project (TO1000112-V1 “3D geological model of the storage complex and set of structural geological maps”, produced in WP2) because the responsible Project Partner of the result was MND. Instead, the internal quality control procedure of MND was used, and the respective QC opinion is attached to the main result document in the ISTA system.

A consultation meeting with TACR was held online on 2 November 2022. It focused on the N_{map} approval process and the corrective measures to be taken by CGS as a reaction to the findings of the financial part of the TACR audit concerning fuel costs calculation.

An important part of the project administration efforts are the public procurement procedures to accommodate the planned sub-contracts and purchases of materials and services needed by the project in full compliance with applicable regulations (in particular applicable public procurement legislation and internal procurement policies of all partners).

A public tender procedure with the aim to award a sub-contract – feasibility study on the applicability of seismic survey for monitoring of the CO₂ plume at Zar-3 for WP7 – was organised in the second half of 2022. Preparing of the public tender started in July 2022. Due to the complicated internal regulations of the Ministry of Environment (CGS is within the scope of authority of this ministry) and due to the necessity to prepare all needed documents in both Czech and English versions (the obligatorily used Czech electronic tool for public tendering – NEN – requires a Czech version, even if the tender is international), the public tender was launched only on October 19, 2022 and was open until November 30, 2022. One bid was received in requested term. On December 15, 2022, after checking the required documentation submitted by the applicant, the CGS representatives (special commission) approved the selection of the applicant - Mr Roman Pevzner, sole trader, Australia - as the “winner” of the public tender. The sub-contract agreement with the supplier will be signed in January 2023. The final delivery deadline for the study is 31 October 2023.

Other purchases of material and services were carried out using the usual procedures of Project Partners.

Task 10.2 work is managed by CGS, benefitting from support of an administrative team headed by Project administrator. All Project Partners contribute to the reporting activities.

Task 10.3 – Economic and financial management of the project

Actual project costs of the first monitoring period 11/2020 – 12/2021 were reported in the 1st Interim Report submitted in January 2022, including relevant documents and other materials. During 2022, all project costs and expenses have been tracked on ongoing basis and continuously compared with approved budget. In December 2022, preparation for financial reporting within the 2nd Interim Report was started. Justification of the costs incurred in the reporting period are provided in chapter 6.

Task 10.3 is carried out by the Project administrator at CGS, supported by the CGS Accounting Department. All partners appointed a person responsible for regular transfers of economic data to Project administrator and provided the required input.

Deviations and changes

The only deviation from the plan is the delay with establishment of the End-User Group. This is now planned for Q1/2023, which still provides sufficient time to engage end-users and other stakeholders of the project and receive the desired feedback on project results.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

Other results		
No.	Result title	Date of submission
R10.2	Project interim reports in ISTA	1/2022

Milestones

No milestones are defined for this Work Package.

3 INVOLVEMENT OF CONSORTIUM MEMBERS IN PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

All consortium members (Project Partners) have been actively involved in project execution in 2022. Their roles and responsibilities are clearly defined in the Partnership Agreement, and, in particular, in its Attachment 6 “Project content & Detailed description of Work Packages”. This document specifies the work and role of each partner in every Work Package and Task in detail.

In the 2nd reporting period, all Project Partners contributed to project implementation according to the plan. No major issues related to cooperation within the consortium were incurred, and the minor ones were successfully solved on the ground of the Management Board. The contributions of individual Project Partners to implementation of the work plan in individual Work Packages and Tasks are described in detail in Chapter 2.

4 JUSTIFICATION FOR CHANGES IN THE PROJECT TEAM

The total actual workload reported in the second period of CO₂-SPICER is 11.55 person-years (FTE), which corresponds to 106.9 % of the plan. This figure corresponds well to the reported progress of the project and the slight deviations reported.

Key persons

There were no changes in the composition of the key persons’ team in 2022, except VSB:

- Matěj Křístek, PhD student, stopped working on the project at the end of 2021.
- Adam Lacman started his work on the project as PhD student in the beginning of 2022. Following the TACR requirement to specifically list PhD students and PostDocs, he was added to the list of key persons in the ISTA system.

The actual workload of most key persons reported for the 2nd project period generally corresponds to the plan. Petr Jirman, a PostDoc at CGS, took fully over the duties of WP7 leader and, due to this, his workload was higher than originally planned. Milan Pagáč, Member of the Research Team and expert reservoir engineer at MND, exceeded the planned workload due to the extensive work on dynamic modelling in WP3 and WP8 that proved to be more time consuming than expected. The higher workload also compensates for the unused capacity from 2021.

Other persons

The CO₂-SPICER project team consists of more than 70 researchers and technicians working in five institutions. It was therefore very difficult to exactly plan the working capacity of each person / position in each year, and in many cases only estimations had to be made for the planning table. Therefore, there are slight deviations in actual working capacities in comparison with the plan at most team members; the actual figures reflect the real requirements of the project and its 10 Work Packages, and are based on the time sheets filled in by each team member. These detailed deviations per person and position are not described in the report for proportional reasons.

Action Plan on improving the gender balance and early-stage career researchers’ involvement

The Action Plan was submitted by the Project Consortium at the beginning of the project as a condition set by TACR for Project Contract signature. The implementation of the planned actions shall be reported annually to TACR within the annual project reports.

The current status of implementation of the Plan is as follows:

1. *Consortium will include 10 female researchers and technicians in the project team from the beginning of the project and increase this number to 15 in the 3rd project year at the latest.*

Implementation: 14 female researches and technicians were involved in project implementation in the 2nd reporting period (7 at CGS, 5 at VSB, 1 at MND and 1 at GFU).

2. *Consortium will engage at least three early-career researchers in the solution of the project during the first project year and increase this number to five in the 3rd project year.*

Implementation: One early-career researcher was newly engaged in project solution in the 2nd reporting period – Adam Lacman (PhD student at VSB), while, at the same time, another PhD student at VSB (Matěj Křístek) stopped his work on the project. I.e., the number of early-career researchers participating in project solution in the 2nd reporting period stayed at three (Petr Jirman – PostDoc, and Jakub Vácha - under-graduate student, continue working in the project at CGS

3. *Project Promoter CGS will appoint a young, early-career researcher as co-leader of Work Package 7 ‘Monitoring’, starting from the beginning of the project, with the prospect of taking over the full WP leadership after gaining sufficient experience and skills, in the concrete from the start of the 3rd project year at the latest.*

Implementation: The PostDoc Petr Jirman was appointed as WP7 co-leader from the beginning of the project and took fully over the WP leadership in full from summer 2021.

4. *Project Partner MND will engage a female researcher to act as co-leader of Work Package 2 ‘3D geological model of the storage complex’ from the beginning of the project.*

Implementation: Lenka Klímová has been acting as WP2 co-leader since the beginning of the project.

5. *Project Partner NORCE will use the established collaboration with the University of Stavanger (UiS) on supervising MSc thesis to suggest and supervise MSc topics related to CO₂-SPICER activities for the students at UiS. Results of the theses will be publicly available and will contribute to increasing involvement of early career researchers and dissemination of the project results.*

Implementation: This activity has not started yet at NORCE. The project and the possibilities for master students to work on the topics will be presented to the students in spring 2023. Their work is expected to be done in early 2024 with the thesis defence after project completion.

In addition to the original plan, VSB has already launched a similar action at their university in 2021. Based on this, one Master thesis has been defended, and work on one Bachelor and one PhD theses were still in progress in 2022, based on CO₂-SPICER project activities and results (see Chapter 2.9 for details).

In general, the status of implementation of the Action Plan in the 2nd project period can be considered satisfactory; good results are reported for all the five actions planned.

5 MANAGEMENT BOARD ACTIVITIES

The Management Board (corresponding to project steering committee) is the Project's governing body responsible for operative project management. It consists of the Project coordinator (Principal investigator), all Work Package leaders and consortium partners' representatives. In the first project period, Management Board meetings were held on a monthly basis (usually on every second Thursday of each month) in form of teleconferences. The only exception was the December Management Board meeting that was organised as a physical event in Brno.

During Management Board meetings, the progress of work in all Work Packages and other issues related to project implantation were regularly discussed. Management Board was also used as a platform for definition of cooperation actions and individual responsibilities, discussion on data hand-over, sharing of information among partners, as well as for checking the progress of actions arising from previous meetings.

Minutes of the 12 Management Board meetings held in 2022 were uploaded to "Documents and attachments" of the 2nd interim report in the ISTA system.

6 JUSTIFICATION OF THE ACTUAL COSTS INCURRED DURING THE REPORTING PERIOD

The reported CO₂-SPICER project costs of the second reporting period are 22,783,490 CZK, which corresponds to 102.5 % of the plan. The cumulative spending since the start of the project (1/11/2020) is 40,846,608, which equals to 87 % of the plan. This means that the underspending of the first reporting period (73 % of the planned costs) has been partly made up.

The main part of the incurred costs belongs to the category of personnel costs (17,713,468 CZK) that correspond to the extensive reported workload of the project team - 11.55 person-years (FTE). From the beginning of the project, 22.36 person-years have been spent on the implementation of the project, which is close to the plan (97.9 % of the planned capacities were consumed).

Budget consumption and main project costs incurred by individual partners in 2022 are described below:

Project Promoter – CGS

Total costs incurred by CGS in the second reporting period were 8,854,750 CZK, which corresponds to 103 % of the plan. Personnel costs of 6,529,161 CZK, corresponding to 7.21 person-years (FTE), were higher than planned (115 %). The reasons are a slightly higher workload (6.98 person-years were planned for 2022), especially in WP2 where the complexity of the geological modelling largely exceeded the expectations, the overall 10% increase in salaries at CGS in September 2022 based on a government decision and the decision to avoid the sub-contract on microbiological analyses of fluids in WP5 by direct employment of the relevant expert, moving thus the corresponding costs (150K CZK) to the personnel costs budget. Planned subcontracting costs (376K CZK) were not

spent due to the change mentioned above and to the postponement of the sub-contract in WP7 to 2023 (see Chapter 2.7 for explanation).

Approximately 63 % of planned other direct costs were spent (555K CZK). Cost savings were used to compensate for the higher personnel costs. Main cost items in this category are:

- Inland travel costs (25K CZK), mainly to Zar-3 site for field survey, and to Hodonín and Ostrava for meetings with Project Partners.
- Conference fees and international travel costs (142K CZK) related to presentation of the project and its results at three international conferences (see WP9 for details).
- Travel costs to project meeting in Norway (184K CZK)
- Spare parts for instruments and consumables in WP5 (136K CZK)
- Spare parts for monitoring instruments, consumables for field work, batteries, chemicals, etc. in WP7 (16K CZK)
- Project meeting organisation in Brno (18K CZK)
- Miscellaneous small office consumables in WP10 (11K CZK)

Project Partner MND

Total costs incurred by MND in the reporting period were 4,930,019 CZK, which corresponds to 124 % of the plan. This partly compensates for a significant underspending by MND in 2021. Personnel costs of 3,149,709 CZK were consumed more or less in accordance with the plan, corresponding to 2 person-years (FTE).

The main cost items in the category other direct costs are:

- Travel costs to project meeting in Bergen (125K CZK)
- SW maintenance costs (669K CZK)

Other direct costs spending in the reporting period is higher than planned; the reason is the improper planning of MND personnel and SW maintenance costs in the original budget that has been corrected in the cost statement (see the 2021 Interim Report for a detailed explanation). The SW maintenance costs were calculated according to the percentage of the use of particular SW modules for the project activities.

Project Partner NORCE

Total costs incurred by NORCE in the second reporting period were 7,247,680 CZK, which corresponds to 93 % of the plan. Personnel costs of 7,039,449 CZK, corresponding to 0.98 person-years (FTE) were consumed, which is 91.8 % of the planned amount. The main reason for this slight underspending is mainly the CZK/NOK exchange rate fluctuation that reflected significant NOK softening in comparison with the planned values.

The budget for other direct costs was considerably overrun with consumption of approximately double of the planned amount (208K CZK). The reasons are a slightly higher amount of travel costs and the necessity to rent special SW for modelling work in WP3 and WP8. The software rental was not originally envisioned, however it became necessary to properly handle the available data and create a reliable PVT model as an input to simulations of CO₂ injection into the reservoir.

The main cost items in this category are:

- Travel costs to project meeting in Bergen (37K CZK) from other NORCE workplaces (Stavanger – Bergen and Oslo - Bergen)
- Software rental costs for WP3 (70K CZK)
- Travel costs to project meeting in Brno (93K CZK)

The overall budget consumption (for first and second reporting periods) of NORCE corresponds to 76% of planned budget, which guarantees sufficient resources for the Norwegian partner to complete their work in the project as planned, despite of the severe exchange rate (NOK-CZK-EUR) fluctuations.

Project Partner VSB

Total costs incurred by VSB in the second reporting period were 1,232,178 CZK, which corresponds to 100 % of the plan. Personnel costs of 660,408 CZK, corresponding to 0.85 person-years (FTE).

Other direct costs consumption (325,360 CZK) was consistent with the plan. Main cost items in this category are:

- Travel costs (86K CZK), mostly to project meeting in Bergen, and also to Hodonín (consultations with project partner MND), to the MND core repository at Lužice and to the Brno project meeting;
- Machine calibration, service maintenance in WP4 (84K CZK);
- Services, repair & maintenance of laboratory equipment in WP5 (34K CZK);
- Consumables - mainly laboratory material for tests and experiments in WP4 and WP5, grinding and cutting wheels for WP4 and WP5, materials necessary for laboratory works like a teflon seal, ultrasound probes etc. (117K CZK)

Project Partner GFU

Total costs incurred by GFU in the second reporting period were 518,863 CZK, which corresponds to 78 % of the original plan. Personnel costs of 334,742 CZK, corresponding to 0.51 person-years (FTE), were higher (130 %) than planned due to a slightly higher workload and an increase in the salaries at GFU in mid-2022. The original distribution of GFU project budget was updated to accommodate the prolongation of on-site seismic monitoring to 2023 (see Task 7.3 for details). The unspent parts of the budget from 2021 and 2022 will be transferred to 2023-2024 to cover the costs related to the prolonged duration of the field operations.

Other direct costs consumption (98K CZK) was lower than the plan. Main cost items in this category are:

- Inland travel costs (11K CZK) to Zar-3 site for field work
- Travel costs to the project meeting in Norway (83K CZK)
- Material and consumables for field work, software (4K CZK)

7 OBSTACLES DURING THE REPORTING PERIOD

The consequences of the tornado that destroyed the MND drilling core repository at Lužice in 2021 still influenced the project work in 2022. The main issues were the complete loss of part of the core material and the inaccessibility of the core repository due to reconstruction works. This caused problems with gathering of additional core samples for experiments in WP4.

The injection step-rate test planned in Task 3.2 for June 2022 had to be delayed to 2023 due to technical issues in the injection well and unavailability of both the maintenance rig and spare fibreglass tubing. This caused delays in some parts of WP3 and WP7 that will need to be made up in 2023.

Some delays were experienced in solution of WP3 (Dynamic modelling). The complexity of the reservoir model, and of the local geological settings in general, proved to be higher than expected. Due to this, the analyses of dynamic data at NORCE and the subsequent history matching process in Task 3.4 could not be finalised as planned. The connected milestone M3.2 (transfer of the simulation model to WP8) had to be postponed to 2023.

Partial delays were encountered in WP4; they were mainly caused by the paternity leave of the WP leader (at NORCE) and have been fully made up within the reported period.

None of the above-mentioned issues represent a critical obstacle that would jeopardize the achievement of the overall project objectives.

8 SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT FOR THE PURPOSE OF PUBLICATION BY THE PROGRAMME OPERATOR

The Czech-Norwegian project CO₂-SPICER, focusing on preparation of the first pilot geological storage site in the Czech Republic, has successfully finished the second year of implementation. The main achievement of this project phase is the finalisation of the 3D geological model of the storage complex. This enabled the start of subsequent dynamic modelling and CO₂ injection simulations. Work also continued on assessment of geomechanical and geochemical properties of rocks building the reservoir and its overburden, a comprehensive risk analysis and testing of site monitoring methods.

Czech version

Česko-norský projekt CO₂-SPICER, zaměřený na přípravu prvního pilotního geologického úložiště CO₂ v ČR, právě úspěšně uzavřel druhý rok řešení. Nejdůležitějším výsledkem této fáze projektu je dokončení trojrozměrného geologického modelu úložného komplexu. To umožnilo zahájit navazující dynamické modelování a počítačové simulace injeckáže CO₂ do úložiště. Pokračovalo rovněž studium geomechanických a geochemických vlastností hornin tvořících úložiště a jeho nadložní těsnění, podrobná analýza rizik a testování monitorovacích metod pro dlouhodobé sledování uloženého CO₂.

9 CONCLUSION

The work in the second project period of CO₂-SPICER was performed according to the plan, with only minor deviations. All main results planned for the period were delivered.

Good progress has been made towards achievement of all specific project objectives:

- Construction of the 3D geological model of the storage complex was completed in WP2.
- Work on dynamic modelling of reservoir behaviour was started in WP3.
- Assessment of geomechanical and geochemical properties of reservoir rocks and caprock has been practically completed in WP4 and WP5.
- Work on assessment of risks related to CO₂ storage in the reservoir has been progressing according to the plan in WP6.
- The second phase of field campaigns of baseline monitoring was completed in WP7, representing important input in the site monitoring plan preparation.
- Work on scenarios of further storage site development has started in WP8.
- Czech-Norwegian cooperation in the area of CCS was fostered not only through intense mutual cooperation between Czech and Norwegian partners of project consortium, but also through liaison with other Czech-Norwegian projects funded from EEA/Norway Grants.

In summary, the achievements of the 2nd project period represent a good basis for successful continuation of the project and reaching all its planned goals.

This report is a result of the CO₂-SPICER project
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More information about the project can be found at
[CO₂-spicer.geology.cz](https://co2-spicer.geology.cz).

PROJECT PARTNERS

COORDINATOR

Programme **Kappa**

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